

CULTiVATE

Food Sharing Governance Landscape Analysis in CULTIVATE hub locations: Milan

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1. Brief methodological note

The analysis of the governance landscape of food sharing initiatives in Milan required a mixture of methods and data sources. In order to maximise comparability between the three Hub cities, we developed a detailed research protocol to conduct the analysis of the food governance landscape. First, three research questions were defined to explore these governance landscapes:

- RQ1: How are regulatory regimes shaping food sharing landscapes, and what is their impact on FSIs?
- RQ2: What are the main place-based enablers for and barriers to sustainable food sharing in the three cities?
- RQ3: What is the influence of the cultural and socio-ecological context in shaping FSIs?

The methodology employed a combination of desk-based research analysis and semistructured interviews with key informants in order to gather relevant data to address the research questions.

1.1 Desk-based research analysis

The online search mostly took place on local repositories, such as those from the local, regional, and national administrations. Members of the city administration partner of each local team provided valuable knowledge to identify relevant repositories. Additionally, this was complemented by Google searches adding key local words. We used a set of keywords for the online search. These were translated into Italian. Local teams also added extra keywords that they thought could be relevant considering the local context.

List of keywords:

- food sharing
- urban garden
- urban agriculture
- community garden
- community composting
- community kitchen
- community cooking
- food waste
- food redistribution
- food surplus
- social and solidarity economy AND food.

Documents were selected when they responded to relevant governance categories such as:

- Local strategic plans and programmes
- Legislation: bills, ordinances, regulations, etc.
- Projects
- Official reports
- Existing studies on food sharing governance of the specific city.

Each Hub location complemented this list with other types of documents that they considered relevant for conducting the analysis in their specific context.

1.2 Semistructured interviews

Each Hub location had to select between three and five participants for each of the food sharing arenas according to the following criteria:

- The sample had to cover the three food sharing arenas, taking into account the priority research topics of each Hub location.
- Interviewees had to have extensive experience in at least one of the food sharing arenas.
- The sample had to include participants who had taken part in the governance of FSIs at a diversity of administrative levels and positionalities.
- The sample had to include food sharing practitioners, government officials in relevant departments or agencies, and others if relevant.
- Most of the participants had to be based in the study location and familiar with its local context.
- The sample had to be gender diverse, and the inclusion of minority populations, when possible, had to be a priority. Each city will recruit a group of at least 10 key informants to be interviewed.

In Milan, we conducted 12 semi-structured interviews, which lasted 40 to 80 minutes. The interviews were recorded and anonymised. We transcribed and analysed them using the qualitative software Atlas.ti.

1.3 Analysis

The codification process for both the grey literature and the semi-structured interviews was based on a tree code category developed from a systematic literature review of academic articles focused on governance and food sharing. An initial tree code was developed and later discussed through a participative process with CULTIVATE partners, a total of 48 participants representing academia, policymakers and food sharing initiatives across Europe. The tree code aimed to identify potential barriers and enablers using two levels of categories. The first level listed eight broad categories of barriers and enablers: actors' discourses, internal organisation, knowledge, participation, regulations, relations between actors, resources, and structural factors. Each category contained a second level of codes representing the most relevant aspects of the first-level categories. We complemented the tree code during the process of analysis of the documents and interviews.

2. Community-Based Urban Agriculture

2.1 Introduction

In Milan, the practice of urban agriculture is widely rooted, mainly with the aim of giving back green and fertile areas to metropolitan territories, which are generally dominated by concrete. In 2018, the “Città degli Orti” research project identified 2,255 vegetable gardens colonies in the Metropolitan city of Milan.¹ More recently, the Cultivate project, which mapped food-sharing initiatives in major European cities, and with Milan as one of the hub cities of study, performed extensive mapping of food-sharing initiatives in the Milan area. These include food sharing initiatives based on growing and farming activities. What distinguishes these types of initiatives is their strong social component, carried out by associations and third sector entities with a strong community vocation, in partnership with local institutions and actors on multiple levels, making food sharing an element of development and inclusion at the local level.

Urban agriculture initiatives generally aim to restore green and cultivable spaces to the community, promote sustainable lifestyles and production, and improve access to food in a fair and equitable manner. However, many of these initiatives do not limit themselves to the ecological dimension alone but supplement it with a range of activities aimed at fostering the creation of social relationships, participatory planning, capacity building and integration of disadvantaged groups. Indeed, many urban gardens, along with the cultivation of plants and herbs, or the keeping of bees (and in some cases livestock), provide additional services such as horticultural therapy activities, hands-on laboratories and workshops, cultural events and educational courses, be those for schools or aimed at agricultural employment.

Worth noting is the double role the City of Milan plays in agriculture. Besides the administrative aspect, it is the major owner of agricultural land lots. In particular, the Municipality owns around 800 ha of the 1700 ha within its administrative border. The other two majors are the Milanese Curia and Fondazione Ca’ Granda, a public entity that manages the central city’s hospital. The Municipality has signed 112 rent agreements with private farmers and third-sector entities for social agriculture. The properties, in many cases, include *cascine* and other facilities, the traditional rural buildings of Po Vally, which are part of the rural landscape and cultural heritage of the city. These buildings are sometimes managed by associations and social enterprises that organise food-sharing initiatives devoted to social inclusion and job reintegration. Examples are CasciNet, Cascina Biblioteca, and Nocetum, which have rental agreements with the Municipality (Interviewee 1).

Milan is home to a complex variety of urban agriculture projects, which differ in the variable focus of their activities, all of which, however, share a propensity for sharing, participation and active citizenship. One of the most encompassing examples of this type of activity, combining food sharing with urban agriculture practices, is probably Un Orto a Milano. This initiative starts with creating a biodiversity garden, accompanied by an agroecological laboratory, educational and discussion spaces on food and environmental issues, and sustainable livestock farming. Many of the initiatives

¹ Cucchi, M., Gambino, D. & Longo A. (2018). Report: *La città degli orti*. https://www.boscoincitta.it/bosco/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/pubblicazioni_citta-degli-orti.pdf

are purely didactic and pedagogical in nature, such as MontessOrto, an initiative of the Maria Montessori Institute in Milan, aimed at promoting synergistic agriculture practices with zero environmental impact among the school's student population. Orto Pedagogico Resistente is committed to raising public awareness and promoting environmental education, especially among children.

Other initiatives, however, have a strongly social focus. It is the case of the Servizio Formazione all'Autonomia, which uses horticulture as a tool for improving the personal autonomy of people with intellectual disabilities. Finally, urban agriculture initiatives are designed from an individual and private perspective in green spaces, such as Orto in Città. This initiative allows individuals and families to rent small plots of land to grow their own vegetables in a healthy way and without pesticides.

Furthermore, squatting individual urban gardens (orti spontanei) have a relevant presence in Milan. These horticultural colonies were the very first experiences of individual urban agriculture, dating back to the fifties of the 20th century. They usually lie in residual spaces and gather several citizens, but, due to their spontaneous organisation, they are challenging to quantify and involve in a programmes.

In the following section, among the many growing initiatives identified in the city of Milan, some of the major ones, marked by innovative character and complementation of cultivation with activities of social orientation, integration, inclusion, and development, have been identified.

Category of food sharing gardens	Description
Individual urban gardens	These are plots of land made available for individuals, families, or friends for cultivating purposes. While here production is typically individualised, we consider it part of food sharing because in Barcelona allotment gardeners share knowledge, skills, tools, and time with neighbouring gardeners. In addition, spontaneous urban garden have a relevant presence which is, however, challenging to analyse quantitatively and qualitatively.
Community gardens	These are gardens for people from a community to use and enjoy. There is a wide diversity of community gardens and different agreements with local administrations.
Educational gardens	These are gardens located in schools and involve students, teachers and, in some cases, experts and neighbours.

Social agricultural initiatives	These are farming projects run by organisations whose primary aim is serving the collective and/or general interest rather than making a profit. They focus on social inclusion or in job integration and reintegration for people in need.
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2.2 Community-based agriculture governance landscape

2.2.1 Regulatory regimes shaping urban agriculture and food sharing gardens

Urban garden regulatory frameworks are primarily developed at the local level in Italy. In 2020, an attempt of providing a national regulation was made with disegno di legge (law proposal) “Disposizioni relative alla definizione di un quadro normativo nazionale di sostegno e promozione alla pratica degli orti urbani”, which was not finally converted into a law.² In contrast, regional and municipal authorities have worked to develop frameworks to organise urban gardens in the last decade. Regional authorities set guidelines and objectives for municipal administrations, the primary laws and policymakers on this topic. In addition, Milan is divided into 9 submunicipal administrative entities, Municipi, to which the management of urban gardens is delegated.

The regulatory hierarchy has on top the regional framework Legge Regionale n. 18/2015, which defines the objectives and strategies for urban edible gardens for municipalities.³ The law defines urban gardens as small land lots in urban and peri-urban areas and focuses on the social and environmental impacts they can provide. It identifies urban gardens as spaces for promoting inclusion, sustainable behaviours, traditional products, active citizenship and socialisation (art. 2). In addition, Regione Lombardia issued Legge 21/2021, which regulates urban and peri-urban agriculture, from large-scale agriculture to individual gardening activities (art. 2. e).⁴ Both frameworks underline the non-profit aims of urban gardens devoted to self-production, educational activities and social inclusion activities. Moreover, the Regional administration issued Legge Regionale n. 35/2017 to regulate and promote social agriculture⁵. This regulatory framework recognises the crucial role of agriculture as a driver to promote social inclusion, job integration and reintegration for fragile people, and the benefits of horticultural and farming therapies (i.e., onotherapy and hippotherapy). In addition, the framework states the possible commercial purposes of these activities, defines the implementation of structural funds, and facilitates the synergies with welfare facilities and offices.

² <https://www.senato.it/japp/bgt/showdoc/REST/v1/showdoc/get/fragment/18/DDLPRES/0/1154950/all#:~:text=Ogni%20orto%20urbano%20non%20pu%C3%B2,di%20attrezzi%20o%20prodotti%20raccolti>

³ Legge Regionale 1 Luglio 2015 n. 18. *Gli orti di Lombardia. Disposizioni in materia di orti didattici, urbani e collettivi*
<https://normelombardia.consiglio.regione.lombardia.it/NormeLombardia/Accessibile/main.aspx?iddoc=lr002015070100018&view=showdoc>

⁴ Legge Regionale 8 novembre 2021, n. 21. *Agricoltura urbana, periurbana e metropolitana*
<https://normelombardia.consiglio.regione.lombardia.it/normelombardia/accessible/main.aspx?view=showdoc&iddoc=lr002021110800021>

⁵ Legge Regionale 12 Dicembre 2017 n. 35. *Disposizioni in materia di agricoltura sociale.*
https://normelombardia.consiglio.regione.lombardia.it/normelombardia/Accessibile/main.aspx?iddoc=lr002017121200035&exp_coll=lr002017121200035&view=showdoc&selnode=lr002017121200035

Concerning urban planning documents, Piano di Governo del Territorio (the urban general plan of Milan) only mention urban gardens as green areas. It regulates the landscape management of the agricultural fields and extensive farming activities.

2.2.2 Community-Based Urban Agriculture Typologies

At the local level, the City of Milan regulates two typologies of horticulture activities: public land lots rented to individuals for self-production or given for free to associations for social inclusion projects, and educational gardens in schools. The Municipality owns the areas and bans the profitable use in all cases. It follows the regional framework and considers urban gardens as a means to promote social inclusion and environmentally sustainable habits. In addition, it delegates since 2002 the management to the nine municipalities, including the organisation of the assignment processes and the control tasks.

Concerning social agriculture, the Municipality signs ad hoc agreements with the initiatives as it owns more than 800 ha of agricultural fields and related facilities. Agreements between food sharing initiatives and private owners are instead complex to analyse as they are not publicly available.

Regolamento Orti Urbani	Each Municipality has a regulatory framework for regulating horticulture settlements and lot rental. The frameworks are generally identical and rent lot for 5 years. They ban the profitable use and assign lots to citizens according to a public call, prioritising fragile people (low income, number of family components and elderly).
Regolamento Giardini Condivisi	Each Municipality receives the tender from associations that want to manage a residual space. Associations must open the garden to public and organise events for the local community.
Vademecum Orti Didattici	The document is the result of a community of practices developed in 2018. It guides schools in building food gardens from the first steps: reaching funds, gathering skills and the possible governance models.

2.2.2.1 Individual Urban Gardens

Individual urban gardens follow the nine municipal **Regolamento per la gestione degli orti urbani**, which regulates land lots for renting between the nine municipalities and citizens. Lots are rented for 5+5 years and assigned through a public call, which yields fragile citizens (low income, number of family components and elderly). Colonies are primarily located in the belt parks, so Municipality 1 has none and Municipalities 5 and 7 have the most. There are 27 settlements divided per Municipality according to the following table:

Municipality 1	0
Municipality 2	3
Municipality 3	1

Municipality 4	1
Municipality 5	5
Municipality 6	2
Municipality 7	10
Municipality 8	2
Municipality 9	3

2.2.2.2 Community Gardens run by Associations

In Milan, two governance models regulate the relationships between association and the administration for the settlement of urban gardens: *Giardini Condivisi*, with the aim to regenerate residual spaces of the urban fabric, and through ad hoc renting agreements of agricultural lands and facilities. In addition, community gardens are in private lots, regulated by renting contracts between owners and associations.

Associations can settle urban gardens in residual spaces thanks to **Regolamento Giardini Condivisi**. Through an agreement with the administration, associations can occupy for free residual and/or neglected spaces owned by the Municipality to create community gardens and promote social inclusion and socialisation. The framework was issued in 2012 and allows only horticultural activities for educational or social purposes. The Municipality cannot guarantee the safety of soils as many residual spaces lie in former industrial areas where soils are highly likely to be contaminated. An example is **Giardino Lea Garofalo**, where the neighbourhood association created a shared public garden in a residual space and a small vegetable and fruit garden for educational activities.

Furthermore, several associations have organised horticulture settlements thanks to ad hoc agreements with public entities (the municipality and park authorities). They created urban gardens for self and community productions, and social inclusion activities and events. In addition, these initiatives include other agricultural activities, such as beekeeping and fruit growing. Two interesting cases are **Orto Comune Niguarda** in Parco Nord Milano, **Orto in Cotica** in Cascina Cotica, and **Orti di Via Padova** in a neglected space in Municipality 2.

Orto Comune Niguarda is located in Parco Nord and it is run by an association that has an agreement with the park authority. It is a community garden that involves the direct participation of citizens. The garden is thus a collective project, based on the principles of sustainable agriculture, environmental protection and local production. Activities that take place in the garden, in addition to vegetable production, include beekeeping, herbs, and womb farming. The garden is self-managed by its members, some of whom are permanent and some of whom are occasional. The main purpose is the inclusion of the community in all levels of planning and management of the garden, for the creation of synergies and social cohesion in the name of a more equitable and sustainable production. Orto Comune engages in a wide variety of social projects such as garden therapy that is also accessible to people with physical and cognitive disabilities, internships aimed at the integration of migrants, and ethnic dinners that combine the dimension of conviviality with that of sustainable and inclusive agriculture.

Orti di Via Padova are urban gardens of Legambiente located in peri-urban areas of Municipality 2 of in Milan, a complex and multicultural context within the city. Their creation dates back to 2014 following the Municipality's granting of land where it was possible to start a project of a shared vegetable garden open to the public. What began as a small reality has since become a positive initiative to promote sharing, togetherness, and social solidarity. In fact, in a short time, the Orti Urbani of Via Padova have expanded their network by collaborating with many local associations, giving back to the neighborhood a green and sustainable space to be enjoyed collectively. Specific initiatives include beekeeping and the reproduction of the bread cycle.

Orto in Cotica is a project carried on by the youth association SpazioTempo, and other partners, which was founded in 2020 to meet the need for social promotion in the area through practical experiences, art, and culture. Orto in Cotica is a community-managed garden open to the public, aiming to create relationships through meaningful projects based on sharing. The project hosts creative workshops for children and experiential labs related to the world of agriculture and cultivation. Additionally, it organises cultural and artistic events within the garden spaces.

Community Gardens in private premises

Besides the food sharing gardens endorsed by the administrations, several initiatives have settled their horticultural and agricultural activities on private land lots. These initiatives have private rental agreements that regulate activities. Examples are: **Coltivando** an urban horticulture initiative inside the Politecnico di Milano lands, **Giambellorto** which is run by the local community of Giambellino, and **Giardino degli Aromi**, which aims at social inclusion and educational activities in the lands of a former psychiatric hospital.

Coltivando is a collectively managed urban garden, co-designed by the Politecnico di Milano together with field technicians and the local community. The garden was born from the collaboration between civil society and the academy, combining the cultivation of vegetables, fruits, vegetables, and herbs with the production of compost and the organisation of educational activities and social gatherings. What is produced in the garden is then distributed equally among all group members who have collaborated in the care and management of the garden. The aim of the project is to reconnect people with nature, using urban agriculture both as a means of promoting a sustainable lifestyle (and way of production) and as a channel for cultivating social relationships at the local level.

Giambellorto is a community garden, located in the Giambellino district of Milan. Those involved in growing the garden share a sustainable vision of agriculture, rejecting the use of pesticides and chemicals in a long-term strategy aimed at producing nutritious, quality food. The garden integrates cultivation activities with educational events such as workshops and laboratories and seed exchanges, also involving people in marginal conditions.

Il Giardino degli Aromi APS was founded in 2003, and operates within what was the former Paolo Pini Psychiatric Hospital. The activities carried out by the initiative are diversified, ranging from educational meetings, to seed exchange and sale of garden produce in small local markets. The association's project has a strong social component, since it uses urban agriculture to facilitate and promote the integration of disadvantaged people, through their direct involvement, the practice of garden therapy and also training internships. The community garden houses horticultural plants as well as aromatic and medicinal herbs. Along with the promotion of responsible and inclusive agriculture, the initiative organises training courses and information meetings open to the entire urban community.

2.2.2.3 Educational gardens in Schools

Educational gardens in schools have a relevant presence in Milan. In 2019, 107 public schools (nursery, primary and middle schools) have activated such activities in their spaces.⁶ In particular, horticulture activities have educational purposes, such as promoting healthy diets and sustainable habits, traditional products, and learning the food supply chain. Schools are in charge of urban garden management, primarily involving teachers, students and parents. Sometimes, schools have the support of the local community for educational activities and management tasks: volunteers, experts and associations. Two interesting examples are **MiColtivo** and **Orto Rinascita**.

Concerning the relationships with local administrations, the Food Policy Office promoted in 2019 a Community of Practices (Comunità di Pratiche) to capitalise on experiences developed and create a vademecum for new school horticulture activities.⁴

⁶ Comune di Milano (2019). *Linee Guida Orti Didattici*.

<https://foodpolicymilano.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Linee-Guida-Orti-Didattici.pdf>

MiColtivo project is carried out by the City of Milan with the support of other partners, including the academy. The initiative aims to create participatory managed school gardens within the city’s public schools. The goal is to educate the youngest about healthy eating through the regeneration of school green spaces and the development of educational activities co-designed together with teachers, who are responsible for integrating them within the school program. MiColtivo, in its structure, promotes not only food sharing, education on sustainable eating habits and collective space management, but also social inclusion and multiculturalism through the integration of different traditions into its activities.

Orto Rinascita is part of the Milan panorama of didactic gardens developed within schools. The garden, cared for by teachers and students together, promotes sustainability education by adopting several circular mechanisms. These mechanisms range from the recovery of seeds from cultivated vegetables to a cooking workshop using produce from the garden, to the recycling of waste oil to create soap bars. The project has seen interest from entities on a regional scale and includes the inclusion of parents within some of its activities.

2.2.2.4 City departments involved in food sharing gardens

In Milan, three departments participate in food sharing gardens (see Table 2) and are sometimes not fully coordinated. Individual urban gardens and shared gardens – their management and assignation processes – are entirely in charge of the 9 Municipalities. Ufficio Food Policy, Unità Agricoltura – the department devoted to agriculture – only manages and coordinates social agriculture initiatives in the agricultural land lots owned by the City of Milan. Educational gardens are promoted by the education department which sometimes works in concert with Ufficio Food Policy.

Table 2: Departments from the City of Milan involved in Food Sharing Gardens

Department	Function regarding urban agriculture
Direzione Educazione	They manage educational gardens in schools sometimes in concert with Ufficio Food Policy.
Area Food Policy, Unità Agricoltura	They only manage urban and peri-urban agricultural activities on lands owned by the Municipality.
Municipalities	They manage and assign individual urban gardens lots and community gardens for associations.

2.2.2.5 Municipal programs on food sharing gardens

The interview with the Head of Ufficio Food Policy (Interviewee 1) revealed that no municipal programmes are active in Milan. Indeed, Giardini Condivisi is a regulatory framework for

associations to enhance residual spaces, and for educational gardens, there is a vademecum to help schools settle such activities.

2.2.2.6 Subsidies and grants

Urban agriculture and gardens can access funds mainly provided by private foundations, while public funds are only available for educational and community gardens with non-profit objectives. Since 2015, Regione Lombardia has activated the public call Orti di Lombardia, which funds 50% of urban educational gardens in schools and collective horticultural settlements. Tenders can apply for a maximum subsidy of 10.000€ for community gardens and 1.800€ for educational gardens. Educational gardens in schools can also apply for funds provided by the Italian Ministry of Education (Programma Operativo Nazionale and Monitor 400).⁷

In addition, initiatives can apply for funds provided by private foundations. Fondazione Cariplo funds non-profit organisations promoting sustainable environments through public calls, including urban agriculture and community horticulture projects. Urban agriculture initiatives can also rely on crowdfunding, the contributions of participants, and sponsorships. In addition, urban gardens cannot gain any economic benefit from their products, as the regulatory frameworks, at the regional and municipal levels, ban selling and any commercial activities.

2.2.2.7 Social urban farm key projects

Box 4

Nocetum association was founded in 1998, in the Porta del Parco Agricolo Sud area of Milan. In 2010, the Nocetum Social Cooperative was created, which to date hosts the Nocetum City Farm project. The initiative aims to promote and revitalise what is a peri-urban area of Milan, strengthening the link between urban and rural locations. This urban agriculture project brings together a diverse set of practices. In fact, apart from fields for growing vegetables, orchards and agriculture, Nocetum City Farm includes livestock farming such as chickens and ducks. The facility takes meticulous care in selecting the products to be grown, opting for local traditional varieties and goods rarely sold in mainstream channels of commerce. The goal of the project is not only about sustainable agriculture, but aims primarily at developing knowledge and promoting social integration on the local scale. In fact, the initiative includes volunteer activities and the organisation of educational trails, accessible to both children and people with disabilities.

Milano Green Way is a social cooperative born in 2004 in the Milano-Opera jail. The focuses on agriculture from the perspective of social inclusion, justice, and community, and their projects primarily target people in prison, with the aim of combating social marginalisation against them. The activities carried out under this initiative are diverse, starting with “Milano Green Way” an urban horticulture space open to the public and the community, and a community nursery, the common garden is managed by the cooperative with the inclusion of disadvantaged people, disabled people, furloughed prisoners, migrants and those put on probation. In addition, the cooperative carries out a series of services such as urban green management and floral arrangements for privates, workshops and laboratories with educational purposes addressed to schools and young people. The common thread of the activities is ecology, aimed at the inclusion of marginalised groups, social justice, and inclusivity on multiple levels delivered through a commitment to sustainable practices.

⁷ <https://www.ersaf.lombardia.it/2024/02/12/avviso-di-selezione-progetti-orti-di-lombardia-2024/>

CasciNet project was created with the aim of regenerating the spaces of Cascina Sant’Ambrogio, in Milan. The structuring of the initiative embraces multi-level food sharing and food growing practices. In fact, CasciNet has implemented a widely varied series of projects ranging from the implementation of community-supported agriculture (CSA) mechanisms to the creation of a Food Forest, that is, a forest developed following permaculture principles, the creation of a community garden of horticulturists and the implementation of proximity agriculture in the lands of the Vettabbia Park. In particular, the latter initiative aims to create an agroecological hub that reconnects the city of Milan with the countryside, to promote more direct and sustainable links between urban and rural areas. What makes this initiative innovative is the desire to build a conscious and sustainable model of urban agriculture on multiple levels, through the participatory design of self-generated social initiatives, including local citizens’ direct involvement.

Cascina Biblioteca is a social cooperative in Parco Lambro that combines food sharing and production with social inclusion. The initiative settle in a traditional rural facility (Cascina) and has 40 ha of agricultural fields owned by the Municipality. It organises job integration and reintegration paths in food production and elaboration for migrants and former prisoners. Cascina Biblioteca sells its products to citizens and shares its surplus with other organisations. In addition, the initiative organises educational paths with local schools and has a library and spaces for local activities in collaboration with the local community.

2.2.2.8 Local urban agriculture synergies in Milan

The local network of actors in Milan, operating in the field of urban agriculture initiatives, is quite dense and complex. Generally speaking, entities from the third sector such as associations, networks and social enterprises predominate the scene, being the main initiators of self-organised initiatives providing services for the community.

Parco Nord is a crucial public entity for urban green initiatives, with many of the initiatives being hosted in its areas. Additionally, the city authorities allocate plots of public land to citizens for growing purposes. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that school gardens across Milan have been established by various public schools within urban areas as part of institutional efforts to promote such practices.

Lastly, entities of religious affiliation are also active in the urban agriculture framework, primarily engaging in activities geared towards social solidarity. This aligns with their longstanding involvement in socially relevant practices, including food surplus collection and distribution, aimed at alleviating food poverty.

2.3 Main enablers to community-based agriculture

2.3.1 The Agriculture Belt Parks and Cascine

The presence of the agricultural belt parks (Parco Agricolo Sud Milano, Parco Nord, Bosco in Città, Parco Lambro and Parco Forlanini) offers land lots already devoted to food production. These parks host several social agriculture initiatives run by third-sector entities (social enterprises, associations and charity organisations). Examples are Cascina Biblioteca, Nocetum, Orto in Cotica and Milano Green Way. In addition, there are urban horticulture colonies run by individuals who sometimes gather in informal networks, such as Orto Comune Niguarda or Orti di Via Padova.

Moreover, the Municipality owns almost half of the agricultural fields in Milan (around 800 ha) and the *Cascine* (traditional rural facilities). This allows ad hoc rent agreements with third-sector entities and promotes innovative initiatives and cooperation with private farmers. (Interviewee 1)

2.3.2 Cooperation: Sharing experiences, skills and spaces

The analysis of the case studies reveals that participants know the importance of sharing spaces and building a community around these topics. Orti di Via Padova, Milano Green Way, Giambellorto, Orto Comune Niguarda, Orto degli Aromi and Orto in Cotica share spaces and skills with other initiatives beyond food production. Food sharing gardens enable synergies among different actors. Indeed, these initiatives gather different participants and associations with different objectives and activities, such as beekeeping, horticulture therapy, educational activities, promoting sustainable habits, job integration and reintegration, and social inclusion. Academia also supports urban gardens. Politecnico di Milano installed gardens inside their campuses and promotes research and data collection on this topic in collaboration with other universities and research centres.

2.3.3 Regional and Private Foundations Funds

Regione Lombardia and private foundations are crucial in funding food sharing gardens. Indeed, they provide funds to activate urban food gardens and social agriculture initiatives. The support from private sources with a philanthropic matrix is as frequent as institutional funding. Fondazione Cariplo is frequently mentioned as a partner with associations and non-profit organisations.⁸

2.4 Main barriers to community-based agriculture

2.4.1 There are few spaces for urban gardens

Although the surface of agricultural fields is considerable (1700ha) and the Municipality owns 800ha, the food sharing gardens cover 17.8ha of public rural areas, 2,22%.⁹ Indeed, there are few horticulture colonies managed by the municipalities and concentrated in the southern peri-urban areas (see *Individual Urban Gardens*). Moreover, the access is limited due to a strict regulatory framework which assigns lots for 5+5 years rent agreement and privileges elderly and low-income citizens.

2.4.2 Limited intervention of administration in management

The lack of central coordination and a specific programme reveals a limited involvement of the Municipal Administration, which mainly manages the assignation process through the 9 municipalities. Ufficio Food Policy only works with some social agriculture initiatives inside the agricultural fields owned by the Municipality (Interviewee 1). In addition, no funds, skills, or technical support are provided for these initiatives, which rely on regional and private foundation funds or participants' contributions. Finally, the involvement of the urban planning department is

⁸ <https://www.ersaf.lombardia.it/2024/02/12/avviso-di-selezione-progetti-orti-di-lombardia-2024/>
Comune di Milano (2019). *Linee Guida Orti Didattici*. <https://foodpolicymilano.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Linee-Guida-Orti-Didattici.pdf>

⁹ Data elaboration from Gambino D., Manfredini F. & Longo A. (2020). *Mappatura degli orti urbani nella città metropolitana di Milano*. La città degli orti - report di ricerca. Milan, Italy: Zenodo, February 4, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3635463>. The result is the sum of the surfaces owned by Park Authorities, the Municipality and local associations.

limited – the urban general plan mentions food sharing gardens as part of the public green facilities.¹⁰

2.4.3 Contaminated soils

Although industrialisation has left many residual spaces in Milan, these areas have high levels of pollutants in many cases, and regeneration with agricultural activities is risky. Soil analysis and remediation costs are too expensive to justify the creation of food sharing garden settlements. Alternatively, initiatives can create boxed and table gardens – by isolating and bringing new soil – but it increases the initial costs (Cucchi et al. 2018, p. 282).¹¹

2.4.4 Initial costs and limited long-term economic benefit

Besides the cost of contrasting contaminated soils, creating urban food gardens requires initial costs for public administrations, associations, networks and individuals. In particular, soil preparation, fencing, building facilities, and connection to the aqueduct and other utilities represent the main expenditures. In addition, a cost-benefit analysis over a long-term period that excludes the initial costs has shown a slight loss for participants (Cucchi et al. 2018, p. 282).¹²

2.4.5 Individual culture

Especially in individual urban garden colonies, an individual culture limits the development of a strong community. This individualised culture promotes the appropriation and privatisation of collective spaces or collective food production. The idea of a right to individual land, tools, and production is widespread, and some people have to adapt their expectations when they participate in community gardens (Interviewee 1). However, there are initiatives some initiatives run by associations and networks that have built strong synergies with the local community and other entities (Orto Comune Niguarda, Orti di Via Padova, Orto in Cotica).

2.4.6 Regulations: No commercial use

The selling ban stated in the Municipal and Regional regulatory frameworks may limit the development of innovative initiatives in urban food gardens, as those run by associations cannot sell their products to reinvest in garden improvements. Although participants share their products inside their community (Interviewee 1), production is limited to self-consumption, and even donation to redistribution initiatives is forbidden. Only social agriculture initiatives, social cooperatives, and enterprises installed in agricultural fields can generate benefits that can be reinvested into their activities.

¹⁰<https://www.pgt.comune.milano.it/vas-rapporto-ambientale/6-valutazione-degli-effetti-ambientali-attesi/63-stima-degli-effetti-ambientali-attesi/631-usi-del-suolo-e-ambiente-costruito/6312-aree-agricole>

¹¹ Cucchi, M., Gambino, D. & Longo A. (2020). *La città degli orti. Coltivare e costruire socialità nei piccoli spazi verdi della Grande Milano*. QuodLibet.

¹² Cucchi, M., Gambino, D. & Longo A. (2018). Report: *La città degli orti*, p. 282.

https://www.boscoincitta.it/bosco/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/pubblicazioni_citta-degli-orti.pdf

2.5 The influence of the cultural and socio-ecological context on food sharing gardens

2.5.1 Features of the city's cultural context particularly relevant for food sharing gardens

Historically, Milan has had an interconnected relationship with its surrounding rural areas, making it a hub for agricultural products and innovations. In addition, its geographical position and features have offered opportunities for horticultural and agricultural activities. The fertile soil and the presence of natural springs have shaped a productive rural landscape. In particular, water management has played a crucial role in making Milan one of the most important producers and a hub for agricultural products movements. The canal system of Navigli has connected the city with the Adriatic Sea, Lombard lakes, and surrounding territories. At the same time, it has provided water for cattle breeding, horticulture, and crops. Around Milan, the presence of *marcite* (water-meadows) are an example of this tradition, which since the XII century, are the result of karst springs management to control irrigation and increase food production.

In recent history, urban gardens and migration have been strictly related. The first horticultural colonies date back to the fifties and were settled by national migrants who came to Milan pushed by industrialisation. The initiatives were spontaneous and located in residual spaces between the rural and urban environments or along infrastructures. Several initiatives are still active in their spontaneous approach, and some are today part of the urban gardens managed by the municipalities or park authorities.¹³

2.5.2 Features of the city's socio-political context particularly relevant for food sharing gardens

During the last 20 years, the local political scenario has been aware of improving environmental and social sustainability. The last four municipal administrations have given increasing attention to these topics by increasing green surfaces and contrasting the high levels of air pollution. In addition to that, the historical relationships between Milan and food production have been used as a driver to build social inclusion and improve the urban and peri-urban landscape. This political and collective awareness of food and its supply chain was highlighted during EXPO 2015 hosted by Milan, which focused on food systems and innovation and the challenges cities will face to guarantee equal access to food. Milan then started to lead the international debate on urban food systems, resulting in the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact signed by more than 260 cities worldwide.¹⁴

The central role of agricultural and food production is also evident in the municipal and metropolitan urban plans and policies, giving agriculture the key role of promoter of social and environmental sustainability. In particular, the Urban Food Policy aims to: ensure healthy food and water for all citizens; promote the sustainability of the food system; promote food education; fighting against

¹³ Cucchi, M., Gambino, D. & Longo A. (2020). *La città degli orti. Coltivare e costruire socialità nei piccoli spazi verdi della Grande Milano*. QuodLibet.

¹⁴ <https://foodpolicymilano.org/milan-urban-food-policy-pact/>

food waste; and support the scientific research in agrifood sectors.¹⁵ The five Distretti Agricoli in the Milan Metropolitan Area aim to enhance the rural landscape through collaborative governance between local citizens, the third sector, and farmers.¹⁶ Finally, Piano di Governo del Territorio (the general urban plan) considers agrifood as a driver for improving the local environment and pushing a sustainable urban development.¹⁷

2.6 Policy Recommendations

2.6.1 To City Council

- Increase available funding and resources (skills and technical staff).
- Consider gardens as municipal facilities rather than generic green areas.
- Create specific programmes for urban food sharing gardens.
- Push the involvement of private sector (directly related to agriculture and not) and landlords.
- Increase the number and access to urban food sharing gardens.
- Increase technician support (both for agricultural knowledge and group facilitation).
- Facilitate soil remediation and analysis.
- Create an advocacy structure for urban food sharing gardens.
- Create a public platform for centralising all information and communicating about gardens and participants.
- Include urban agriculture in urban planning and policies.

2.6.2 To private sector

- Consider funding food sharing gardens, also as fringe benefits.
- Create food sharing gardens in private premises or open to social agriculture activities.
- Partner with other organisations to manage food sharing gardens located in private premises.

2.6.3 To Food Sharing Gardens

- Increase participation and accessibility.
- Promote facilitation tools among participants
- Increase skills, tools and fund sharing
- Consider applying to public or private funding.
- Create a network of urban gardens and gardeners to have a higher political pressure and reach funds.
- Improve communication of activities.

¹⁵ Comune di Milano, Fondazione Cariplo, & Economia e Sostenibilità (2018). The Food System in Milan: Five Priorities for a Sustainable Development. <https://foodpolicymilano.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/04/FP3-ENG-FINAL-WEB.pdf>

¹⁶ Branduini, P. (2020). I distretti agricoli milanesi: dei laboratori di paesaggio alimentare?. In Working papers. Rivista online di Urban@it (2), pp. 1-7 https://www.urbanit.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/BP_Branduini.pdf

¹⁷ <https://www.pgt.comune.milano.it/vas-rapporto-ambientale/6-valutazione-degli-effetti-ambientali-attesi/63-stima-degli-effetti-ambientali-attesi/631-usi-del-suolo-e-ambiente-costruito/6312-aree-agricole>

2.7 Conclusions

This report considers the main initiatives emerging from the Cultivate mapping, the interview with Interviewee 1 and the Città degli Orti research project. Although the initiatives identified are relevant in the local landscape, they represent a part of Milan's entire food sharing garden situation due to presence of many spontaneous initiatives. The data gathered in this report shows some of the most relevant aspects shaping the governance of food sharing gardens in Milan.

The report has categorised the different types of these initiatives and the elements that explain their diversity. It has described the principal regulatory framework affecting these gardens, and identified the Municipality's main areas involved with them and the primary sources to fund their activities. The report also identified the main barriers and enablers, and analysed the cultural, socio-political, and ecological contexts.

The findings reveal that food sharing gardens cover a minimal part of urban agriculture areas, and there is a low interest in the local administrations. The lack of coordination and specific programmes limits their expansion and the dialogue with and between the stakeholders involved. The City of Milan seems to be prioritising social agriculture initiatives – social cooperatives and enterprises – rather than individual and association urban gardens. This aspect seems to agree with the regional and municipal regulatory frameworks, which focus on the social benefits of urban food sharing gardens.

Moreover, one of the most striking findings is the limited presence of the private sector on this topic – only a few initiatives are private landlords who rent lots for urban gardens. Involving this sector could become an opportunity to mobilise funds, expand gardens, and involve additional social groups.

The lack of a community gardens network may limit future developments. Although difficult to realise due to the different objectives and actors involved, a comprehensive network – even an informal one – build a solid political pressure which may recognise common barriers and enablers, and reach more funds.

3. Food Recovery and Redistribution

3.1 Introduction

Food recovery and redistribution in the City of Milan is an established practice whose main traditional references are the dozens of secular and faith-based soup kitchens scattered around the city and the food aid distribution fostered by the long-term established Regional Food Bank.

Most of the existing practices were only known locally and the system wasn't coordinated until 2014, when the city of Milan, together with other prominent institutions, instigated the first urban scale assessment. It happened in preparation for EXPO 2015 *Food for the Planet, Energy for Life*, and revealed nearly 200 organizations managing food for solidarity, mainly recovering and redistributing healthy and nutritious food (e.g.: interviewee 1). This is still the reference to measure the scale of the practice in the city, whereas more difficult and ever-changing was the recognition of the food donors. These same early days of growing attention on food waste, combined with the emergence of food poverty, created in the City of Milan an appetite for rationalizing the system that in the long run ended up in the design and implementation of the Local Hubs against food waste.

Ten years later, on the 5th of February 2024 the City of Milan organized a press conference to explain the city strategy - Actions Against Food Waste in Milan, *From Local Hubs to Open Market Recovery* - Even if the title doesn't include *redistribution*, free delivery for human consumption is meant to be the core of the action. These policy traits are analyzed further in this document. As an inconsequential preamble, a couple of insights from the opening roundtable are noticeable.

President of Foody – Sogemi (the Largest wholesale Market in Italy) Cesare Ferrero, pointed out that *food recovery and redistribution* should be observed as a part of the widest scenario in which food is becoming a scarce commodity being subjected to market rules (e.g.: Cesare Ferrero speech at World Day Against Food Waste 05/02/2024). Milan needs nearly 6 million meals per day and the Lombardy Region altogether nearly 30 million per day. This makes room for an inquiry into whether the food system can provide such a quantity of food, possibly fresh, for everyone at an affordable price. If not, a combination of growing food poverty among people (only affluent citizens can afford fresh nutritious food) and unfair competition among companies (to raise margins by counterfeiting origin, expiry date, etc.) might happen.

Deputy Mayor Anna Scavuzzo eagerly appraised the participation of representatives of the entire profit and non-profit food recovery and redistribution supply chain. This social conglomerate created an unprecedented one-year-long co-designing process with some 36 civil society organizations and 72 people manifesting their interest at the co-designing kickoff meeting. Nevertheless, a lack of media coverage was underlined, which parallels the little interest from the press that arose around the Milan Food Policy protocol.

These two interventions suggest that the governance of the *food waste recovery and redistribution system* must envisage itself inside the food business global trend on the one hand and must reach

public opinion on a systematic base on the other hand, maybe using creative languages and alternative media.

Between these two extremities (macroeconomics and individual sensitization), there is space for big progress in each link of the food recovery and redistribution supply chain to increase it, rationalize it, and make it fully sustainable.

3.2 Food recovery and redistribution governance landscape

3.2.1 Regulatory framework

There are several layers of strategies, policies, laws, and regulations affecting Food Sharing Initiatives in Milan. In the context of Food Waste Recovery and Redistribution, it is possible to congregate on Global, European, Italian, Regional, and Urban scales. In the first round of interviews and consequent follow-ups that shaped this report, the discussions touched upon the ones below:

The Good Samaritan Law L. 155/2003¹⁸.

The Gadda Law L. 166/2016¹⁹.

The Recognition, Protection, and Promotion of the right to food. Region Lombardy L 34/2015²⁰.

The Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point. HACCP (93/43/EEC, L. 155/97, EC Regulations 852 and 853)²¹.

The Milan Urban Food Policy Pact. City of Milan 2015²²

The Milan Food Policy. City of Milan Resolution 25/2015²³

EU Farm-to-Fork Strategy.²⁴

Few actions (namely L. 155/2003, L. 166/2016, RL. 34/2015) were referred to as “vertical”, hence specifically impacting specific subjects, as other actions were intended as horizontal, hence landing more on stakeholders indistinctively even if with different levels of engagement. Vertical and horizontal actions provide boundaries to a framework that is comprehensive and readable and yet somehow unaccomplished. The following paragraph summarizes the contents recalled by interviewees and reports their comments therein expressed. Looking at it from a different angle shows that Laws, seen as top-down, binding regulations, started shaping the general framework

¹⁸ LEGGE 25 giugno 2003, n. 155 Disciplina della distribuzione dei prodotti alimentari a fini di solidarieta' sociale. (GU Serie Generale n.150 del 01-07-2003)

¹⁹ LEGGE 19 agosto 2016, n. 166 Disposizioni concernenti la donazione e la distribuzione di prodotti alimentari e farmaceutici a fini di solidarieta' sociale e per la limitazione degli sprechi. (16G00179) (GU Serie Generale n.202 del 30-08-2016)

²⁰ Legge Regionale 6 novembre 2015 , n. 34 Legge di riconoscimento, tutela e promozione del diritto al cibo (BURL n. 46, suppl. del 10 Novembre 2015)

²¹ Decreto Legislativo 26 maggio 1997, n. 155 "Attuazione delle direttive 93/43/CEE e 96/3/CE concernenti l'igiene dei prodotti alimentari" (Gazzetta Ufficiale n. 136 del 13 giugno 1997 - Supplemento Ordinario n. 118)

²² Gabinetto del sindaco deliberazione n° 25 del 5/10/2015 (Verbale di deliberazione del Consiglio Comunale)

²³ Linee di indirizzo della Food Policy di Milano

²⁴ Farm to Fork Strategy. For a fair healthy environmentally friendly food system. EC 2020.

from the beginning, while policies, seen as participatory, co-designing strategies, came later, maybe leveraging on the prior.

The **Good Samaritan Law** L. 155/2003 was designed at national level to encourage donations of ready and surplus food, also in the context of catering which would otherwise be thrown away, and to facilitate the activity of organizations that distribute meals and food to the deprived, for free. The law equates the "final consumer" with non-profit organizations that carry out, for charitable purposes, free distribution, relieving them of all complex and bureaucratic requirements. In practice, non-profit organizations that recover food, for example, from organized catering to deliver it to soup kitchens are not required to comply with the rules on food safety, because they are considered equal to the final consumer. The Law does not imply that, by simplifying regulatory obligations, safety practices for the treatment of cooked and fresh foods will no longer apply. Indeed, the identification and application of the correct procedures for the recovery of food is a shared responsibility of each subjects involved, but with a new and higher moral character that derives precisely from the free and spontaneous adherence to the culture of giving and recovering food.

Even though the Good Samaritan Law was received enthusiastically, it did not translate into a sudden implementation because of the technical knowledge, management skills, and investments that organizations should undergo to make the system cost-effective. For example, collecting fresh and cooked food from canteens implies completely different logistic management combined with transport and conservation capacity than managing packaged food. Only a few remarkable programs like Siticibo from the Food Bank Foundation started soon after the Law was enforced and lasted in time.

The **Gadda Law** L. 166/2016 was designed at national level after a process that involved all the actors in the recovery and redistribution of food surpluses. It intends to make the current Italian regulatory framework more organic and simplify, update, and engage more Civil Society Organizations in actions against food poverty. Its key points are:

To create a regulatory framework within which to insert the already existing rules regarding tax breaks (L. 460/97, L. 133/99), civil liability (L. 155/03), and procedures for health and hygiene safety (L. 147/13).

To provide a taxonomy with a clear definition of food sector operators, transferors, food surpluses, food waste, donation, minimum shelf life, and expiry date, etc.

To grant to Public Authorities the faculty to donate confiscated food to non-profit organizations.

To facilitate the donation procedures over the waste disposal procedures.

To prioritize recovering for human consumption over animal consumption, and biofuel.

To set a Coordination Table at the ministry level for the consultation of all stakeholders involved in the fight against food waste and poverty. Also, an increase of 2 million euros to the existing National Fund to purchase extra food.

To plan communication campaigns on RAI, the national public broadcaster, to encourage companies to donate and raise consumer awareness on food waste.

To encourage the practice of gleaning.

To enable municipalities to incentivize food donors with a reduction in waste tax.

The first eight points touched by the Law created an enthusiastic atmosphere around food donation and engaged more small community-level organizations, more retailers, and more volunteers. The latter point was a specific lever for municipalities to engage more food donors in their constituencies. One of the criticisms arose around the fact that the Government allowed only a partial tax deduction specifically on the quote collected by Municipalities making it less appealing for taxpayers. The City of Milan, at the time of the launch of the food policy, worked with a working group to put the reduction in use on what was called TARI (Tassa sui rifiuti / Tax on Waste) the local tax borne by estate users intended to finance the costs of the waste collection and disposal service. The city tried to elaborate for a long time, also with practical experimentations without producing significant results. A working group with the private sector was also coordinated, together with the City of Milan fiscal department and Third sector representatives. Initial experiments were carried out throughout a pilot year in 2018, involving around fifty operators in these monitoring, but then not generating an effective discount in the new tax. As mentioned, although the Central Government allowed the detaxation, it is up to single cities to activate this lever independently to attract more food donations. This didn't happen automatically, and an accurate National study is not available yet. Even on the company side, this leverage is not fully effective. Food waste is generally tackled by increasing process efficiency and elongating product life through diverse marketing strategies. From a purely financial point of view, many efficiency innovations are seen as a better solution than a donation even if related taxes are reduced. From a strategic point of view, supermarkets donate food surplus to the nearest organizations to tighten the relationship with their communities, increase their reputation, strengthen customs loyalty, and possibly achieve new customer acquisition. Where food receivers are not available in the vicinity, food donations lose their power, and the decision returns to the realm of financial efficiency and confronts the cost of transport and financial delays. There is room for a wider application of L.166/2016 especially on the company side among the small retailers who were hardly informed of the opportunity. On the food receiver side, the discussion is open on the opportunity to receive food too close to the expiry date as it might end up as waste anyway if they can't use in time. Another interesting bottleneck is the possibility of food receivers (non-profit organizations) processing food donations making them last longer and re-selling them. This is a legal vacuum that creates uncertainty.

“Our company recover many other goods other than food so that we didn't get much gain from the detaxation on food waste tax partial reduction”.

(Interviewee 4)

The **Law 35/2015 Recognition, Protection, and Promotion of the right to food**. was approved by the Lombardy Regional Government to ensure the universal right of access to enough safe, healthy, and nutritious food as a fundamental human right for all individuals in the Lombardy Region. The main points addressed in the law were:

- The Lombardy Region undertakes to eliminate all forms of malnutrition and poor nutrition within its territory, promoting policies to combat poverty and supporting the reduction of food waste.
- The law defines key concepts such as the "right to food," "food waste," and "food surplus."

- Access to food sustenance: Norms and policies are introduced to ensure access to the necessary means for food sustenance for all, supporting public and private initiatives aimed at combating poverty.
- Combatting food waste: Actions are promoted to raise awareness and train actors in the agri-food sector and consumers about the risks of food waste, encouraging the progressive reduction of waste and rewarding companies that adopt virtuous practices.
- Recovery and redistribution of food surpluses: Initiatives for the recovery and redistribution of food surpluses to disadvantaged groups are supported, with incentives for companies adopting these practices.
- Regional Consultation for the Promotion of the Right to Food: A regional consultation body is established to promote the right to food, tasked with contributing to the definition of regional objectives and strategies for promoting this right and monitoring the results achieved.
- Food and health: Programs for food education and psychological support are promoted to improve awareness of the benefits of proper nutrition and a healthy lifestyle.

The regional Government also approved an evaluation clause, a mechanism for periodic evaluation of the implementation of the law, and achievement in promoting access to food, reducing waste reduction, and redistribution.

In summary, the law aims to guarantee the right to food for all Lombard citizens, promote policies to combat poverty, raise awareness about food waste, and facilitate the recovery and redistribution of food surpluses. It also pledges financial provisions.

In fact, in compliance with L 34/2015, the Regional Government of Lombardy has announced a regional public selection for the provision of contributions for the financing of innovative projects for the benefit of:

- agri-food chain, which goes from the production of agricultural raw materials to the disposal of the related waste, for the benefit of consumers and economic actors involved.
- processes and activities relating to the design and production of food, packaging, logistics, and marketing to enhance the market and have a significant impact on consumption dynamics
- sustainable agriculture (protection of biodiversity, diversification of the agricultural landscape and ecosystems, production systems with reduced environmental impact, etc.) and multifunctional agriculture inspired by the principles of agroecology.
- shelf life of food products and their packaging, aimed at limiting waste and using food surpluses
- dissemination of information that enhances food throughout the supply chain, useful to consumers in general or aimed at targets of particular interest.

The funding was made available to a wide platform of beneficiaries such as public bodies, universities, qualified non-profit organizations, civil society organizations, trade associations, foundations, public and private entities that operate for profit, and freelancers in the agri-food business, allowing them to group in consortiums.

For such an effort to conceptualize the funding and for such an ambitious plan to enforce L 35/2005 the funds approved were quite small with some €200,000 allocated for each of the 2021 and 2022 financial years. For each of the 6 to 20 expected applications, expenditure eligible spanned from €20,000 to €60,000, which in the case of food waste and redistribution investments would cover a few technological advancements.

The **Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point (HACCP)** system is the widest legislative framework that encompasses the food waste and recovery system, which is also a baseline standard for whoever wishes to operate in the food industry. It consists of a set of procedures aimed at ensuring the wholesomeness of food. It is a system based on the identification, monitoring, and subsequent analysis of the dangers of contamination of food products. Besides being mandatory, this system is acknowledged for its scientific basis that provides adopters with a ready-made system suitable for controlling food when it is being processed which translates into the self-control manual. Born in the USA in the 1960s and developed by NASA to combat the spread of food-borne diseases and to guarantee, at same time, food safety, after the 1980s has spread

*“HACCP is the first regulation to refer to in order to guarantee health for those who eat food. Therefore, those who deal with recovery must be careful to handle food according to this regulation”
(Interviewee 6)”*

throughout the world to become the **only universally accepted method for guaranteeing food safety**. In Italy, since 1998, every organization that carries out the preparation, transformation, manufacturing, packaging, storage, transport, distribution, handling, sale, or supply, including administration, of food products must equip itself with an **internal self-control plan**. This means constantly verifying the hygiene of the product, checking all phases of production where a risk to the health of the consumer can arise, and demonstrating this commitment with suitable documentation that can be readily consulted by the **Control Authority**. The HACCP system was introduced into European legislation with Directive 93/43/EEC and transposed into Italian law with Legislative Decree no. 155/97, more recently replaced by the new EC Regulations 852 and 853, which require all European food sector operators to apply procedures based on the HACCP system, excluding those who deal with primary production, for example growers and breeders, who must however respect the rules of good operating practice. Currently, proper self-control must follow 7 fundamental principles such as hazard identification, the definition of critical limits, the definition of monitoring procedures, the definition and planning of corrective actions, the definition of verification procedures, the definition of registration procedures, and hygiene self-monitoring activity. **The Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point** systems are admittedly costly and binding, but every actor in the food recovery and re-distribution supply chain, from grower to consumer, accepts it as a guarantee for quality.

The **Milan Food Policy** was signed in July 2014 by the City of Milan and the Cariplo Foundation, the Italian largest philanthropic operator established in 1991 by accomplishing the reform of the banking system (Amato/Carli). From then onwards, every banking foundation including Cariplo became an independent juridical entity with full statutory and management autonomy, required to pursue goals of social utility and promotion of economic development. Some relevant sectors were indicated such as scientific research, education, art, healthcare, conservation and enhancement of cultural and environmental heritage, and assistance to the most vulnerable. Cariplo Foundation

included food waste reduction and food poverty mitigation in its area of interest supporting the building up of the Milan Food Policy.

The City of Milan, through the Food Policy activities, also creates relationships and exchanges experiences with various Italian cities diffusing good practices and improving its own experiences. Primarily, the Food Policy involves entities in its metropolitan area, secondarily collaborates with many Lombard and Italian cities that are undertaking positive actions in production, transformation, food recovery, recycling, and disposal.

The Milan Food Policy also advocates for MUFPP (see next section) among Italian cities channeling its vision throughout and connecting, smaller and marginalized cities with over 200 cities at European and international levels. The **Milan Food Policy – An action plan for the improvement of the local food system** stemmed from a deep analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of the Milanese food system, the related elaboration of objectives through public consultation, and the adoption of a common City Council Resolution for the MUFPP and the Milan Food Policy²⁵. The Milan Food Policy contains 5 priorities, to guarantee healthy food for everyone, promote sustainability for food systems, food education, tackle food waste, and support and promote research in the agri-food sector. The Fourth priority indicates the fight against food waste, has a series of directions that impose the municipal administration to work to redistribute the surpluses in its territory, promote an environment of growth for all operators active in the sector, and reduce food waste as much as possible, even in public services, by analyzing it. So, once again school canteens, green markets and relations with large-scale organized distribution. The Strategic and legislative framework provides some solid ground for food recovery, recycling, and disposal actions to establish and grow, not to mention a revived public opinion attention on food waste and food poverty that encourages Milan Council to operate with wide consensus. All interviews and further conversations indicate that there is a growing interest in all sectors of society regarding the sensible production, distribution, and consumption of food since the pandemic-related crisis has shown everyone how vulnerable the food system is when considered merely as a commodity rather than a fundamental human right. On an urban scale, few people and operators are extending the debate on food scarcity and food poverty to the climate change global issue, whereas most just focus on small-scale solutions.

The **Milan Urban Food Policy Pact** (MUFPP) is the main legacy of the Universal Exhibition “Expo Milan 2015” Feeding the Planet, Energy for Life. The MUFPP is a global commitment of mayors from around the world that considers food as an entry point for the sustainable development of growing cities. **Being born in Milan, whose name is embedded in the Acronym, MUFPP created a surplus of commitment in the City of Milan Administration.** It represents the main framework for cities and international stakeholders active in the definition of innovative urban food policies. Milan Pact’s framework for action is the result of a participatory process among 46 cities that worked together in 2014, under the guidance of a technical team of international experts, on the definition of 37 recommended actions structured into 6 integrated categories (*Governance, Sustainable Diets and Nutrition, Social and Economic Equity, Food Production, Food Supply and Distribution, Food Waste*). Although all the categories foster a wiser usage of nutritional resources, the *Food Waste* one contains consistent guidance with this report.

²⁵Linee di indirizzo della [Food Policy di Milano](#)

The MUFPP Food Waste specific action aims at convening food system actors to assess and monitor food loss and waste reduction at all stages of the city, region, and food supply chain, (including production, processing, packaging, safe food preparation, presentation and handling, re-use and recycling) and ensure holistic planning and design, transparency, accountability and policy integration. It also raises awareness of food loss and waste through targeted events and campaigns and identifies focal points such as educational institutions, community markets, company shops, and other solidarity or circular economy initiatives.

The MUFPP category **Food Waste**²⁶ (Action 34, Indicators 41, 42) provides recommendations to city leaders and policymakers who want to reduce food waste by adopting a circular economy approach. Indicator 41 measures the total annual volume of food losses and waste with a focus on **food recovery and redistribution for human consumption**. Indicator 42 measures the annual number of events and campaigns aimed at decreasing food loss and waste, some of which are resolved in redistribution.

The MUFPP category **Save Food**²⁷ (Action 37, Indicator 44) provides recommendations to facilitate recovery and redistribution for human consumption of safe and nutritious foods, if applicable, that are at risk of being lost, discarded, or wasted from production, manufacturing, retail, catering, wholesale, and hospitality. Indicator 44 measures the totality of available food recovered and redistributed for direct human consumption along the entire urban food supply chain, occurring from the time at which availability is recorded (in urban and peri-urban areas) until it reaches and is used by the final urban consumer as food. Data is collected to assess safe and nutritious food recovered and redistributed for direct human consumption at various system stages (production, handling and storage, processing and packaging, catering, distribution and point of purchase, household/ consumption). It also suggests measuring types of food recovered/redistributed for human consumption as well as the energetic or nutritional content of different types of food waste/loss.

The MUFPP category **Social and Economic Equity** (Action 14, Indicator 18) provides recommendations to city leaders that want to address inequality and poverty related to food systems such as using forms of social protection such as cash and food transfers, food banks, community food kitchens, and emergency food pantries. The scope is to provide access to healthy food for all citizens, to encourage and support social and solidarity activities, to promote networks and support grassroots activities, to promote participatory education, training, and research. Indicator 18 measures food insecurity and indicator 19 the take-up (or usage) of food and/or social assistance support through programs that target vulnerable groups.²⁸

MUFPP has attracted new cities every year since its creation, positioning itself as a global reference for Urban Food policies. Besides this horizontal expansion, there is space for interaction with global or multilateral organizations such as the EU (Eurocities working group food), FAO, and WFO. On 12 January 2024, the Italian Development Cooperation Agency published a call for proposals open to Civil Society Organizations in Africa, in which appeared Urban Food Policy among the predefined areas of interventions, after a long-lasting consultation with MUFPP. The impact of MUFPP resides

²⁶ Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, 15 October 2015. [Food Waste](#).

²⁷ Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, 15 October 2015. [Food Supply and Distribution](#).

²⁸ Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, 15 October 2015. [Social and Economic Equity](#).

in its capacity to recall attention on urban food-related issues, put them in a wider context, facilitate information circulation, and smoothly transcend moral suasion. The simple fact that MUFPP headquarters is in Milan makes the city accountable. And guarantee the continuity of its commitments to its own Food Policy.

The **Farm to Fork Strategy** of the EU is at the heart of the European Green Deal aiming to make food systems fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly. The EU clarified its position by stating that *Food systems cannot be resilient to crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic if they are not sustainable*. According to the EU, food systems need to be redesigned because as of today they account for nearly one-third of global greenhouse gas emissions, consume large amounts of natural resources, result in biodiversity loss, have negative health impacts (due to both under- and over-nutrition), and do not allow fair economic returns and livelihoods for all actors, for primary producers. EU also envisages new opportunities for operators in the food value chain, stating that *new technologies and scientific discoveries, combined with increasing public awareness and demand for sustainable food, will benefit all stakeholders*.

“It was an extraordinary intuition of positioning Milan at the top of the food agenda before anyone else”
(Interviewee 1)

The Farm to Fork Strategy aims to accelerate the European transition to a sustainable food system that should:

- have a neutral or positive environmental impact.
- help to mitigate climate change and adapt to its impacts.
- reverse the loss of biodiversity.
- ensure food security, nutrition, and public health, making sure that everyone has access to sufficient, safe, nutritious, sustainable food.
- preserve the affordability of food while generating fairer economic returns, fostering the competitiveness of the EU supply sector, and promoting fair trade.²⁹

The Strategy also contains a proposal for a **legislative framework for sustainable food systems** (FSFS) considered one of the flagship initiatives of the Farm to Fork Strategy. Initially, it was expected to be adopted by the Commission by the end of 2023 therefore it was published for public feedback from 28 September 2021 until 26 October 2021. This feedback period offered all interested parties, including citizens, the possibility to contribute to the policy-making cycle. Although 230 contributions were received, food recovery and redistribution actions are still not directly mentioned in the strategy.

In the EU, nearly **59 million tonnes** of food waste (131 kg/inhabitant) are generated annually with an associated market value estimated at **132 billion euros** (Eurostat, 2022). Eurostat roughly estimates that around **10% of food made available to EU consumers (at retail, food services, and households)** may be wasted. At the same time, some **32.6 million people** cannot afford a quality meal every second day (Eurostat, 2021).

²⁹ Farm to Fork Strategy. For a fair healthy environmentally friendly food system. [EC 2020](#).

Food waste also has a huge environmental impact, accounting for about 16% of the total greenhouse gas emissions from the EU food system.³⁰

Reducing food waste has enormous potential for reducing the resources we use to produce the food we eat. Fighting food waste is a **triple win**: it saves food for human consumption; brings savings for companies and consumers; and lowers the environmental and climate impact of food production and consumption.

The EU is committed to achieving the global Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Target 12.3 - to halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer level by 2030 and reduce food losses along the food production and supply chains.

These targets reflect on policies at an urban scale or at least provide a reference for them.

It is worth also mentioning **EU strategies against food waste** 2011/2175 (INI) that expressly linked food waste with combating hunger, as well as the **FAO National Waste Prevention Program** PINPAS 07/10/2013 that stressed measuring food waste prevention at source and linked recovery through donations to charities. Although each of the pronouncements created spaces for the Milanese food system stakeholders to speculate, discuss, react, propose, and imagine, one single event in the last twenty years addressed strategically the discourse around food in the City of Milan. This was EXPO 2015 Food for the Planet, Energy for Life, the universal exhibition that turned the spotlight on urban food policies and committed the City to the matter. Among the many global issues and macro trends discussed, there were spaces for many actors from civil society to manifest their interest from many angles. Building up one single large event gave a chance to the National Government, Regional Government, City Government, Universities, Private operators, Civil Society Organizations, NGOs, and the Third Sector to submit their ideas and projects (some 200 proposals were collected) most of which converged on food waste recovery and redistribution. This is relevant because when the City of Milan and Fondazione Cariplo undertook the Milan Food Policy co-designing process, they could count on a *shared ecosystem* for the City of Milan *to navigate with ease*.

The overall legacy of EXPO 2015 is summarized in the two programmatic documents, The Milan Charter (“Carta di Milano”) and the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFFP). The Charter was signed by millions of citizens and the Pact by over one hundred cities around the world (now over 200). Such a level of participation sanctioned the fundamental role of citizens and cities, their concrete contribution to the food policies, and the ability to translate each food policy into daily actions, implemented by all citizens.

The **Milan Food Policy** refers to these principles and positions the City of Milan as a guarantee for the connection, integration, and direction of all actions to both, making objectives clear and making activities more effective, plus, to verify if actions are attaining the objectives of sustainability, resilience, equality, and inclusivity. The Milan Food Policy is Centered around the City of Milan and led through participatory governance whose principal components can be summed up as follows:

- institutional coordination in the mayor’s cabinet through the appointment of the **deputy mayor** and the setting up of a **Board of Interdepartmental Coordination**
- technical support for coordination provided by the **Food Policy Department**

³⁰ Eurostat. Statistics Explained.

- long-lasting support guaranteed from the memorandum of understanding with **Fondazione Cariplo**
- Scientific and technical support from **ESTÀ** (an independent and non-profit research, training, and consultancy center bridging scientific knowledge, policies, and active citizenship).
- inclusion of other Milanese stakeholders through the **Metropolitan Food Council**
- monitoring, analyzing and evaluating the Food Policy and the dynamics of the food system.

3.2.2 Programmes and Initiatives Governance

The Local Hubs Against Food Waste programme is an attempt to create an urban-scale model of food recovery and redistribution in the City of Milan. As specified before, the 2015 Milan Food Policy's Fourth priority indicates the fight against food waste as one of its main pillars. This principle materialized in the design of the 2018 city program Local Hubs Against Food Waste, a small-scale system progressively replicated in different Milan Urban Districts. Although many informal, intermittent, or temporary forms of food waste recovery and redistribution are possibly going on in the city, it is correct to refer to the Local Hubs as a city-wide policy underlying a governance system.

As of today, five Hubs have been activated, Isola Hub in the 9th Municipality, Lambrate Hub, in the 3rd Municipality, Centro Hub in the 1st Municipality, Gallaratese Hub in the 8th Municipality and Foody Zero Waste Hub, created inside the wholesale market in Calvairate in the 4th municipality. In 2023 this network allowed to rescue 615 tons of edible food from waste and give it to people in need.

In 2024 three new Local Hubs will be ready to start, the Cuccagna Hub in the 4th Municipality, the Selinunte Hub in the 7th Municipality, and the Multiple Hub in the 2nd Municipality. With this increase, the programme is covering 7 out of 9 city districts (Municipalities).

The functioning of each Hub follows guidelines provided by the City of Milan, given that the core of activities is the recovery and redistribution of food from nearby businesses. The model includes key elements such as:

A network system. Each hub funnels food donations from different sources more efficiently than pre-existing direct contact between supermarkets and single non-profit organizations that hardly manage single-product peaks and won't be able to manage fresh and cooked food. Generally, hub managers, which are non-profit organizations with experience in the sector, try to provide their clients, both families and organizations, with the most complete food provisions. Since supermarket donations are not predictable in quality and quantity, they are often complemented with non-surplus food that can be purchased, received from individuals, received from regional food banks, or received through the Fead (the fund for European aid to the most deprived of the EU).

A monitoring scheme. Centralisation also means better and more comprehensive control of recovery and at the same time a wider knowledge of food poverty. This implies that data is shareable and software is integrated.

Adequate physical locations. Hubs need to be in strategic positions and spaces with furnishings able to manage fresh food, cooked food, dry food, fruit and vegetables, and bread. This implies a cold room for fresh food, shelving for dry and packaged food, and an administrative area for the archive

and procedures. It also implies the presence of a van equipped with a cold storage room and a second vehicle to recover surpluses from company canteens. Nevertheless, each hub adds specific services that better serve its constituency purposes. Centro and Gallaratese for example both include Solidando, a social market where credit scorecards are given to beneficiaries who become therefore accountable for their families' food recruitment. Centro includes a bakery lab that transforms food donations such as flour, salt, sugar, yeast, eggs, and herbs into bread, sweets, and other products with added value for their beneficiaries.

A peculiar experience is represented by the Foody Zero Waste Hub, launched in a pavilion of the wholesale market, thanks to the "Foody Zero Waste" call initiated by the Cariplo Foundation in conjunction with the City of Milan. The winning submission was entitled "Value Project", (promoted by the University of Milan together with Recup, the Italian Red Cross - Committee of the South Milanese Area, and the Lombardy Food Bank). It made it possible to consolidate the recovery activities already present at the Market by aggregating some new realities with other entities already present at the Market such as Caritas Ambrosiana, Eco dalle Città and Pane Quotidiano.

A common framework. As mentioned above, the governance of the Food Hub initiative guarantees contributions from different perspectives. On the food donor side, Public Administration, Academia (Politecnico, Statale University, Està) and Philanthropy (Fondazione Cariplo with "QUBÌ", its main program against child poverty) are also supported by Assindustria, the largest company association advocating and representing the food industry. No second level organizations are involved from the third sector. These disparities might indicate that, paradoxically, the profit sector understands cooperation better than non-profit does. This is left to further speculations.

Given common guidelines each of the eight hubs creates individual protocols in terms of procedures (acquisition of beneficiaries, services integration, human resources management, volunteers management, location management) and sustainability (funding mix, strategic partnership) providing a variety of interesting solutions.

Some 10 managing organizations are part of the network, Banco Alimentare della Lombardia, Caritas Ambrosiana, Comunità nuova, Croce Rossa, Eco delle città, Fondazione Arché, IBVA, Magma, Recup, Terres des Hommes.

Some 12 main food donors are part of the network, Bennet, Carrefour, Conad, Coop, Erbert, Esselunga, Getir, Glovo, Il Gigante, Lidl, Naturasì, and Pam.

Two Hubs are experimenting a slightly different models:

- Foody is built inside the Fresh Food Market and focuses on a daily recovery of fruit and vegetables thanks to some organizations that bring their volunteers day in and day out.
- Multiple Hub covers a wider area by creating multiple collecting points.

Stable and resilient food recovery and redistribution initiatives have become part of the Local Hub network and those that are consolidating will have the opportunity to enter through future co-designing processes. The Local hubs aspire to become a reference model for operations on an urban scale, a sustainable network that brings together people, organizations, and businesses. The City of Milan has developed a familiarity with the primary actors as representatives of the associations and City officers that are now exchanging at a personal level. This facilitates informal consultations when

new needs or project opportunities arise or when parties gather in the so-called *communities of practice reunions* organized cyclically, generally once a year (or when it is deemed appropriate).

The City of Milan describes these communities of practice *as moments of mutual, real, lived, non-theoretical exchange of experiences*. Calling them *communities of practice* cements the idea of communal intentions, of the desire to work together, and the intention to share proposals and solutions. Participant organizations might not share this view yet, since many years of *competition* left them a bit mutually suspicious. Even so, it happens more and more that not only do proposals and solutions derive from ideas but also from virtuous experiences told and discussed among participant associations, encouraging the transmission of knowledge on which future collaborations and networking actions can potentially be based. It is acknowledged that, even if the City of Milan brings its agenda and priorities to the table, modifications or improvements may arise from discussions with the participant organizations. This flexibility means that the communities of practice could be considered the actual place of synthesis and synergy between stakeholders and could represent a *neutral place* in which to reconcile the interests of individual operators, effectively overcoming many historical contrasts. This harmonization of relationships is also a good ground for monitoring the overall distribution and observing trends over time, thanks to the collaboration with the Polytechnic of Milan as a scientific partner.

“We wish to encourage more associations, even coming from different sectors, to start a recovery and redistribution area of work”.

(Interviewee 1)

The City of Milan involves corporate representative bodies (namely Assolombarda) in its governance system that can advocate for single associates. This bond is facilitated by the collaboration with Polytechnic University which has activated the Food Sustainability Independent Observatory, the observatory on food sustainability which is supplying vertical research on food waste to the private sector, typically large-scale supermarket brands. Each supermarket brand provides aggregated and disaggregated data monthly to Polytechnic:

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Aggregated data:

- Production (turnover) - Donation
- Waste disposal

Disaggregated data per food group:

- Dry (various products including bread, pastry)
- Fruits and vegetables
- Meat
- Fish
- Gastronomy and cured meats
- Dairy products
- Rotisserie

Even if actively participating in the work of the Observatory, the City of Milan Policy leaves the direct interaction with the private sector to the University, although The City of Milan can access and monitor data together with Polytechnic and private businesses. Direct operations remain between

companies that generate food surplus and non-profit associations that collect and redistribute it, with the Polytechnic of Milan facilitating the relationship between large-scale distribution and the individual non-profit organizations managing the hubs.

The singularity of this collaboration is also represented by the **control room**, created jointly by the City of Milan, Polytechnic, and Business representatives. This makes data reading transparent as well as allowing a comparison of the impact of the Local Hubs on single Supermarket brands. These coordination events are very important because they incorporate the point of view and the forecasts of businesses in the analysis of the trends. So, as an example, the Observatory could anticipate if a decrease in the overall capacity for redistribution is expected in August, or if in the month before Easter a large availability of baked food and little meat is expected.

In the **control room** with businesses, as in the case of the **communities of practice** with non-profit representatives, everyone gives and receives pieces of information so that knowledge is shared. This has meant over the years, for example, a greater dissemination of good practices that some supermarkets had developed with diverse civil society operators or in other urban contexts, and good practices for the reuse of surpluses developed inside the supermarkets themselves.

The control rooms are very positive spaces for collaboration because they are seen as third-party infrastructures from individual stakeholders. The equal representation of public administration, academy, profit, and non-profit (Cariplo Foundation advocate for non-profit sector) guarantees impartiality and neutralizes partisan biases. This unlocks a level of collaboration that in other contexts remains blocked by corporativism and competition.

The Local Hub experience is emblematic of the relationship of the City of Milan with the third sector. The Hubs are formally managed by non-profit organizations as per Italian legislation, that is engaged through public notices and selected through public tenders issued by the municipality of Milan. This way, transparency, and equal opportunity are guaranteed. As the tender's mechanism suggests competition, the regulation itself and the City of Milan's moral suasion incentivize Co-competition among candidates.

Consequently, an agreement is activated between the City of Milan administration, a non-profit organization, and other project partners lasting four years (or occasionally for longer periods). This represents the hard-core relationship. The officers of the City of Milan and the individual operators then have informal encounters weekly and at times even daily, to work practically and less formally on data collection, problem analysis, and the emergence of critical issues to which they collaboratively try to find solutions. This can be the case of food scarcity, when hubs with more food can rebalance, or vice versa, food abundance (i.e. single products, perhaps perishable), when hubs with free space available can store them.

“We have a very careful system to track the products that are approaching their expiration dates before they become waste. Also, it makes little Ecological sense to save food from waste by transporting it to a food receiver fifty kilometers away”.

(Interviewee 4)

The non-profit organizations recovering fruit and vegetables from the markets (Recup and Eco delle città) don't have any formal relationship with the City of Milan, but only an operational agreement.

The authorization of the recovery and redistribution of fresh fruit and vegetables in municipal markets is not required. Initially, the City of Milan and the associations tried to clarify the issue with the Milan Health Agency to have a clear ruling and possibly promote the activity to other subjects, given the good results obtained at an informal level. Since little was achieved, the City of Milan then suggested that the same organizations apply their model inside the publicly owned space of the Foody fresh food market. In doing so, all the experience and the operational capacity acquired informally on the street market could be applied in a more regulated space.

One single event that boosted the Milan Local Hub experience was the awarding of the EarthShot Prize 2021 to Comune di Milano, which, besides the encouragement received from a prestigious independent commission, granted 1 million pounds to invest in the program.

This opportunity allowed the City of Milan to improve and strengthen its current initiatives related to food waste such as the Local Food Hub, but also to explore new opportunities along the entire food waste value chain, to strengthen existing Hubs, funding new ones, to monitor the impact of actions within a verified framework and to allow the development of new synergies between the players in the system.³¹

The Local Hub strategy is paying off, based on a solid network of stakeholders fully committed under the strategic coordination of the City of Milan.

Nevertheless, scaling up means managing a growing complexity while keeping the system efficient and sustainable. Key issues will be promoting **innovation** (e.g. cooked food has the highest added value but is complex to manage), integrating **logistics** and **transport** (e.g. City hubs have limited capacity and can suffer peaks or scarcity of variety), implementing uniform **data management** (e.g. organizations have different monitoring systems), guaranteeing **software interoperability** (e.g. warehouses and supermarkets uses different formats), avoiding **overlapping** (without data exchange beneficiaries can use different hubs), easing **competition** (charities often recover donations individually), guaranteeing **continuity** (supermarkets more and more promote last minute sales of valuable products) and avoiding **secondary waste** (food too close to their limit are sometimes accepted).

In smaller cities, let alone the ones outside the Milan metropolitan area, cooperation is more difficult. Supermarket chains like Coop Lombardia for example revealed that their sphere of influence exceeds the Urban scale, so their operations are mostly determined by their wider internal policy rather than being fragmented into many different ones according to many territorial splits. There are virtuous cities like Milan or Varese, where they proactively collaborate with the Food Policy but in most cases, their hypermarkets are too big for single beneficiaries and need to organize up to 5 daily deliveries to 5 different non-profit organizations 5 days a week. Many Cities are too small to think about a food policy or some hypermarkets are too big to refer to one city only. In many smaller cities there is little or no coordination among non-profit organizations and between them and their Municipalities. They might occasionally attend the same cultural events to talk about food waste but won't cooperate in practice. Even in Milan this governance model is still in progress, some non-profit organizations see the benefit of participating in the Local Hubs as a model for coordination, but still rely on other complementary activities. Many other smaller organizations

³¹ The EarthShot Prize 2021. [Build a Waste Free World.](#)

carry out micro activities that can hardly be included in one of the Local Hubs given the existing threshold in size, organizational capacity, and funding.

3.2.3 Different perspectives on food recovery and redistribution

To signify the diversity in various food-sharing initiatives related to recovery and redistribution it is necessary to use a paradigm among the few offered by interviewees.

A first perspective divides **top-down** initiatives promoted by the Administration (i.e. Welfare departments) from **bottom-up** initiatives initiated by grassroots organizations. The main difference resides in the **access to services and goods**, subject to strict rules, controls, and procedures in the first case, whereas universal access is often granted in the latter. Given that beneficiaries in most cases overlap, it looks like a double standard from a policy perspective.

“Although goals and type of beneficiaries are the same, the difference in ease of access is obvious.”
(Interviewee 2).

A second perspective divides **coordinated** from **uncoordinated** initiatives. The first category includes occasional micro food recovery of any sort, from any shop, and with little or no logistics. This operativity does not need supervision, matches the unique needs of single associations in their communities, and can diffuse where needed around the city reaching shops of any size. Indeed, food in excess can hardly be redistributed when not used hyper-locally. On the other side of the spectrum, there is a coordinated recovery system, organized at the urban scale, that increases efficiency by creating synergy among various operators (i.e. hub managers can optimize the redistribution of big provisions of the same items). Optimizing costs often means choosing bigger food donors over small businesses and consequently losing vital community relationships with artisan and shop owners, favoring relationships with corporate managers. Relationships with artisan and shop owners also facilitate being knowledgeable of community needs, local opportunities and mobilize volunteers. The dualism between coordinated and uncoordinated is seen as an alternative since the two habits can't coexist. Acting locally and uncoordinated is also perceived as independence and self-determination. The differences between these two approaches are judged insignificant when the task is recovering cooked food from canteens because it presents a series of technical and managerial difficulties that can only be implemented by specialized operators.

A third perspective categorizes the initiatives by the **type of food they recover**. According to this view recovering predominantly fresh food, preserved food, or cooked food provides a specific character to the whole organization. Mainly because this determines the food donor they are linked with, the workers they hire, the volunteers they attract, or the organizations and individuals they serve.

A fourth perspective divides **resilient** practices from **non-resilient** ones. In the period from Expo 2015 to now, the City of Milan has assessed, observed, and sometimes supported dozens of initiatives that did not become fully operational and, therefore were discouraged. Some made it through to the present day and generally were incorporated into the Local Hub initiative described above. The resilient practices as described can count on a consolidated network system, a monitoring dashboard, adequate physical locations, a peculiar experience, and a common framework. The standard logistics model provides two daily recoveries from supermarkets of unsold

packaged fresh and dry food, loose and/or packaged fruit, and surplus bread, storage in the Hub, and distribution to charity organizations in the afternoon. So far only one hub can guarantee cooked food daily using its insulated van for just-in-time withdrawals from canteens.

Resilient initiatives are also those developed when the Pandemic caught Milan off guard which will be detailed in the Social Solidarity Economy section.

Besides the Local Hubs, other initiatives are showing that the system can become more resilient when stakeholders cooperate systematically.

Non-profit organizations managing Local Hubs also started recovering uneaten bread and fruit from some 100 canteens in public schools of Milan.

A special Hub was established inside Foody, the Fresh Food Market allowing a few organizations to recover fruit and vegetables directly from the wholesalers. Fruit and vegetables rescued here are qualitatively good products, possibly farther from the expiry date because business-to-business sales grant a longer shelf life to produce.

Some youth-driven associations started operating on the street markets (regulated by the City of Milan) by collecting unsold fresh fruit and vegetables from traders directly at their stalls and redistributing it immediately on-site to vulnerable groups they engage and assist regularly.

A fifth perspective classifies initiatives considering the **complexity** of the model whereas food recovery and redistribution can merely happen between two subjects or consist of a complex interaction of stakeholders.

- The end users can be individuals, families, residents in communities, or recoveries
- The charities organizations can be associations, cooperatives, social enterprises, foundations. Or Civil Society Organizations
- The managing organizations can be any of the aforementioned working on food operation exclusively or integrating food operations with multiple services
- Businesses can be food donors, in-kind donors, financial supporters, technical supporters, sponsors or provide free loans for premises.
- Street markets, Indoor markets, and public markets can cooperate on food recovery

“Another fundamental issue is whether there is a governance structure dedicated to food, or a strategy that has the specific objective of redistributing surpluses. It depends on whether there is a dedicated team. In Milan, there is certainly a rather high level of maturity.”
(Interviewee 2).

A sixth perspective is the **operational management models**. The traditional recovery and redistribution of surpluses leverages donations from companies and redistribute to charity organizations. Within this cluster, the initiatives differ mainly by the heterogeneity of the products managed, according to the level of intermediation. Then there are the social supermarkets, social shops, or solidarity emporiums which grant social cards directly to beneficiaries. There is the emerging transformation of food donations to extend food residual life. Finally, the shop donations, in which private citizens shop and give part of their food shopping anonymously.

A seventh perspective is the **scale of intervention**. Some initiatives work at the neighborhood level, some at the municipal level, and others act across the entire city.

An eighth perspective is based on the **level of integration** public vs profit vs non-profit.

Some initiatives are created and coordinated by large organizations that can count sometimes on larger networks, bigger budgets, and different references than a

“Our cooperative was always aware of people in need in the communities, but in recent years the gap between classes is more visible and food poverty touches more and more people”.

(Interviewee 4).

policy led by a public administration. In the city of Milan for example the Food Bank, which is a private organization and Coop Lombardia, which is a consumer cooperative. Both operated a long time before the City of Milan adopted its food policy. The Regional Food Bank is affiliated to a national network, which is related to a European Federation that is connected to a Global Food Banking Network. Indeed, this means that it responds to a pre-existing set of values, a strong expertise, a consolidated operational model, and a network of relationships at the institutional level that might create friction while starting afresh at the micro level. Coop Lombardia started more than 20 years ago donating food to charities, even before any state or regional regulations were passed, before having its corporate social responsibility policy, and its internal food policy. This followed a pure altruistic attitude at the beginning adding value to the communities where they lived. In the Lombardy region, 60 Coop supermarkets recovered food surplus and donated to some 137 charity organizations operating in several different modalities. Some charities package supermarkets' surplus and deliver it to families, there are soup kitchens that use recovered food for their daily meals, and there are associations that process surplus to extend the product's life. The social cooperative il Giglio, of the Caritas network, had specialized in processing food donations together with purchased food to create frozen provisions then distributed in their channels for a longer time, responding to more needs. The capillary contact with micro-communities is very valuable for the Cooperative as these daily exchanges are also critical to understanding the market. Last, but not least, the long commitment to food recovery and redistribution increased the feeling of belonging of many employees who volunteered in supplementary activities like training the charity operators. Both Coop Lombardia and Lombardy Food Bank successfully cooperate with the City of Milan in the Local Hubs, but this might cover a fraction of their global activities and possibly not the core of it. The hard talks come when the discussion turns on the integration of software, data sharing, and volunteer management.

A ninth perspective is based on what type of beneficiaries the organization chooses to support. Due to the scarcity of food one can choose to give less to many, often lowering the criteria to access the programme, another can choose to specialize in specific needs of predetermined targets (i.e. Children, communities)

A tenth perspective is the ultimate driver of the initiatives that can be more on environmental protection or social protection.

An eleventh perspective is based on the people that an organization chooses to involve which can be predominantly hired professionals, paid workers, or volunteers.

As stated at the beginning of this paragraph different perspectives were identified to classify food waste and recovery initiatives offering specific angles to look at it. In the attempt to uniform the taxonomy, they can be tagged as:

Direction: top-down vs bottom-up

Entropy: coordinated vs spontaneous

Expertise: conserved vs fresh vs cooked food

Sustainability: resilient vs non-resilient ones

Complexity: triple actors vs multiple actors

Purposes: food only vs integrated services

Scale: micro-level vs urban level

Integration: public/profit/non-profit

Beneficiaries: extensive vs intensive covering

Goal: environment vs social

Human resource: professionals vs volunteers

The eight local hubs currently active in Milan can be analyzed according to any of the previously mentioned paradigms or a combination of them, positioning an initiative towards a variable rather than its opposite. The multitude of approaches that the hub managers offer is considered a value if a good level of coordination is provided.

Although operators choose their approaches based on their core values, traditions, and available resources, overall efficiency needs to be assessed. Given the variety of approaches, it is important to evaluate when a system is sustainable (where its resources come from) and when is circular (neutralizing its footprint, minimizing its waste).

3.3 Motivations behind food sharing

From the City's perspective, the most important push factor to catalyze the attention of stakeholders was the concreteness of the path that the administration undertook after having formally approved its food policy in the city council.

Businesses and organizations, even if they were reluctant in the beginning at the idea of the administration dealing with things outside its mandate, reconsidered during the co-designing

"In the beginning, many operators look at the City interest as opportunistic or propagandistic".

(Interviewee 1)

phase. In the journey that led from the establishment of a small, dedicated office to the consolidation of an entire department, the City of Milan gained the status to dialogue with long-established operators competently. Mutual trust has increased over time, leading to results

exceeding expectations and this increases the motivation of all stakeholders. Now everyone sees more clearly the change in the system and the desire to attack waste by working together.

The Food Bank, the largest and most expert non-profit operator in the field of food recovery and redistribution reported that its motivation stems from taking pride in providing an operational model to the city and consequently satisfying more of the people in need.

Non-profit organizations are also interested in seeking funding since they are mostly volunteer organizations. Working within the Hubs also gives those who do not deal exclusively with food recovery the opportunity to receive reserved public funding. Alongside direct public funding, there are also sponsorships from businesses that benefit from the recovery. The visibility given by participation in the hubs also increases the possibility of collecting private donations in cash or kind. Emblematic is the case of some physical spaces of the Hubs given out by private individuals for free, but whose investment remains in the owner's assets (is it tax-free? What is the advantage?).

Businesses started considering food donations mostly after Law 166/2016 made it possible for Municipalities to reduce tax waste for companies who donated food. Since this is left to the cities to decide and since it only applies to the variable share of the tax, the fiscal leverage had little appeal. Even VAT deductions on donations (donations are fiscally accountable as sales and company can book it as tax credit) appear to be a blunt factor for company motivations.

Other elements seem to leverage business motivation more such as visibility, customer satisfaction, and employee engagement. The City of Milan designed an ethical logo that food donors can apply to their shops when they enter the Local Hubs programme. Most clients become loyal to supermarkets that commit to reducing waste and helping people in need. Employees are often volunteering in community-based non-profit organizations dealing with food aid and are happy to add up part of their working hours when agreed with the employer. Not to mention presenting food aid-related activities to their managers. Companies are motivated also by their own vision that may induce companies to

“Our employees are our true heroes since they committed to understand recovery methods, even if it was easier for them to dispose food.”

(Interviewee 4)

support food-sharing initiatives even if they work in different industries. Fondazione Milan, Banca di Credito Cooperativo di Milano and Fondazione Snam are main partners of the local Hub programmes even if they are derivatives of businesses non related to food (sport, banking, and commodities). Corporations indeed are including themes such as sustainability and circular economy in their company strategies.

3.4 Storytelling of Food recovery and redistribution

In Milan, the dominant player in the system of recovery and redistribution of food surpluses is the Food Bank (Banco Alimentare della Lombardia), the leading active player throughout Italy with its 20 regional branches, integrating logistics on a national scale.³² This actor is the most important and has also been the most reluctant to coordinate its activities with the Food Policy on an urban scale. Especially at the beginning, they saw the City of Milan as having an opportunistic attitude in working

³² [Fondazione Banco Alimentare.](#)

on this issue, given that its institutional mission was not generally that of recovering surpluses. Over the years, the Food Bank acknowledged that the City of Milan's interest was purely to strengthen the system and enable more actors to cooperate, obtaining a systemic advantage. After 10 years, the Food Bank is increasingly an active partner of Milan's Food Policy, having consolidated a mutual trust with the City of Milan.

In public opinion and some media observers, there is an overall systemic narrative that stems from the paradox of a consumeristic society where corporations and consumers induce food overproduction and waste for exclusively commercial reasons, the same society that simultaneously leaves to the goodwill of some the food recovery and redistribution for beneficial purposes. Even if the system worked with maximum efficacy, recovering and distributing 100% of the surplus products, it would remain inefficient compared to a system that rebalanced production and consumption without the pursuit of maximum gain. In this sense, even system corrections applicable to businesses like tax leverage or compliance

“Certamente lo spreco alimentare è parte del nostro sistema alimentare, bisogna farsene carico, cercando di destigmatizzarlo”.

(Interviewee 1)

to donate unsold food are affecting the symptoms rather than the cause. This might lead some to think that recovery and redistribution are part of the problem because they are embedded in the consumeristic ideology.

The City of Milan, operating as the umbrella organization of the Urban Food Policy, limits its responsibility to that of a facilitator of a system of private actors that rebalance the system on the two sides of food waste and people's needs.

There are other divergent views among stakeholders. Some believe that food aid policy cannot be left to the initiative of citizens and associations. The public body must take care of the poor trying to respond to their needs, however complex and costly from an organizational point of view. Food recovery and redistribution policies surely help to mitigate problems but cannot be the only response to food poverty. There are two main reasons, the food recovered is not enough, and the distribution industry is increasingly efficient *always learning new ways to sell up to the last minute of product shelf life*. Also, it is not ethically correct *to give to the last the discard of the first*. In this vision it is accepted to use surpluses as an additional help, but not as a prevalent channel.

Then there is a narrative that promotes the private social sector and the notion of subsidiarity, in which the recovery specialists, those who know how to do their job better than anyone else, must be facilitated and the public body must mainly remove the obstacles so that they carry out their work more easily or must simply fund their operations. Some discordant voices point out that public welfare cannot delegate the problem of food poverty because otherwise its effectiveness in responding to other problems that are connected decreases, such as child poverty, educational poverty, and welfare in general.

There is another narrative related to fostering people's autonomy, whereby the poor have the skills and resources to manage food recovery by themselves and those who want to help should limit their support to facilitate the process. This trend has generated interventions at the street market level where some organizations recover fruit and vegetables for immediate distribution to the

needy. These tactical actions tend to respond instantly to an immediate need in a manner disconnected from the rest of the people's necessities.

Food poverty can therefore often be addressed alternatively inside public welfare or within market mechanisms itself. Mainly research institutions pointed out that the food recovery and redistribution narrative is influenced by an initial lexicon problem. The basic terminology adopted is not uniform among those who disseminate ideas and contents. The Italian terms *spreco*, *scarto*, *rifiuto* (all decline the English word *waste* in three different meanings), and *eccedenza* (surplus) are sometimes confused and overlapped. Some research institutions try to raise awareness of the differences, but this should be accounted for with accuracy among the press and the media. Everyone should follow the definitions recognized by the European Commission and echoed in national laws. The words one uses are the basis of one's narrative. If on the one hand, the recovery of surpluses and their valorization for social purposes is now a widespread practice, on the other hand, a negative bias survives. Negative prejudice resonates when the *waste*, characterized as food that no one wants, is destined for the *marginalized* and by analogy people that no one wants (lesser valuable people). The narrative becomes unpleasant and declassifies the practice. An error in the use of words has the power to transform the perception of readers or listeners. Within this downward narrative, there are also pessimistic tendencies in which companies donate food *opportunistically* and organizations *misuse* it.

There is a positive narrative that highlights the environmental, economic and social value of food recovery and redistribution, sometimes using words like *donation* and *care* in describing the process but, the communication that points out the positive impact is taking place at a more rational level so might be less powerful than the negative one.

The different operational modes sometimes are built around different principles, values, and cultural attitudes even if they agree on avoiding mechanisms that make beneficiaries depend on aid and subsidies. Sometimes food hubs are connected to charities that reorganizes food in parcels, possibly balanced in nutrients and quantity according to the size of the receiver and deliver directly to the beneficiary's home. This helps override social stigma that occur being seen at "poor people places" or soup kitchens and strengthen personal relationships among beneficiaries and operators who can bridge emergent needs other than food to the welfare operators. To some this is seen as encouraging a passive attitude in receiver that needs to be activated and take charge of a vital task as providing food for themselves and their families. This goal is more easily achieved offering to beneficiaries an affiliation to a solidarity market and fostering their active role in buying (virtually) their own food shopping.

3.6 Main enablers of food recovery and redistribution

3.6.1 Increased awareness in public opinion

Most actors agree that from Expo 2015 there's a great visibility on every aspect concerning food. Then the COVID-19 related crisis sensitized the public opinion on the food poverty emergency. Milan was hit the hardest and the earliest, with news amplifying the iconic images of the empty shelves in supermarkets. Then the war in Ukraine, brought a feeling of insecurity in Europe after so many years, with its direct impact on energy prices and the indirect impact on food availability. The combination of food popularity and social insecurity made it clear that some problems need to be challenged at a systemic level so that issues like recovery and redistribution skip to the top of the social agenda. Policymakers were sensitized, food donors were attracted, and overall corporate social responsibility was stimulated.

"Before, people of an elevated status understood deprivation only at an intellectual level. After the Pandemic forced everyone to experience spatial reclusion and scarcity there's also an emotional connection with people suffering deprivation"
(Interviewee 7).

3.6.2 Urban Food Policy and the Coordinator role of Municipality

Having an Urban Food Policy is seen as an enabling factor. It drafts a shared vision, provides a helicopter view on problems and solutions, activates resources, connects actors, provides forecasts let alone mobilizing public fundings. Public-private-partnership increase the scope and scale when resources are being systemized. A good example is the free concession of both private and public premises to non-profit organizations to develop their hubs that were conditionally granted to that specific destination.

Still, not all the prospects partake in the Local Hubs program, there are possibly 10 social markets in Milan (besides IBVA, also ARCA, Caritas and Terzo Paesaggio opened theirs) and at least 40 non-profit associations active with continuity in food recovery and redistribution (37 manifested their interest in opening new Hubs) so that the challenge is to make the system more inclusive without losing efficiency.

3.6.3 The dense urban fabric

A definite enabling factor is the density of the city's urban fabric which offers favorable conditions for micro actions. The main players are concentrated in certain areas at the neighborhood level or below. Proximity helps optimize logistics and strengthen relationships. The widespread presence of local covered and uncovered markets is also a crucial node because such venues concentrate many donors in a single place and because they generate surpluses of great nutritional value such as fresh fruit and vegetables.

3.6.4 Subsidiarity

One crucial factor for success is the set of skills, networks, and relationships that today exist and have been structured in all the municipalities of Milan. Combined with the state's commitment to the theme of the food aid economy, it could allow urban-scale politics to work with a view to the continuity and maintenance of good practices even in the long term.

3.7 Main barriers to food recovery and redistribution

3.7.1 Changes in the political scenario

From the Administration's perspective, the main obstacle to the Policy is its continuity. Being able to maintain the commitments that have been made within the existing institutional and regulatory contexts. Working for the recovery and redistribution of surpluses is not a regulatory obligation and it is not an institutional competence formally assigned to Municipalities by law. Therefore, a change of administration could decide to reverse the trend and therefore divert staff to other policies. And it would be a legitimate choice. Or a new direction could choose to work only on one of the sectors currently active.

3.7.2 Slow and complex bureaucracy

Another obstacle is linked to administrative procedures, which are often long and are seen externally as an unbearable burden. However, the management of public money in Italy is subject to more rigorous controls than in other states. From this point of view, the complexity of the administrative procedures protects the system from possible offenses that would ruin the reputation of a system largely based on trust (think of the thousands of volunteers).

"Sometimes charities attitude is parochial. After the emergency was over, they went back to managing their own backyard"
(Interviewee 4).

3.7.3 Limited cooperation and individualism

Companies see a limit in the mentality of many small associations that fail to cooperate. An example is when during the Pandemic crisis there was a need to coordinate efforts, they didn't accept to make their data available to the institutions. Even the emergency task force arranged in those days is remembered as an *extremely difficult journey* due to petty jealousies.

On the business side, the lack of knowledge of regulatory instruments and incentives represents a limitation. Another critical point is that most companies fail or are not interested in measuring the food surplus. The structuring of the whole process passes through measurement. Some companies don't even put in place measurement systems at all because they don't see their importance.

3.7.4 Progressive decrease of food surplus

On the non-profit side, one of the barriers or limiting factors is the decrease in food available due to the increase in efficiency of all business channels. Many companies reacted to the COVID-19-related crisis to re-design their systems aimed at reducing waste.

The catering sector has revised their organization and even the smallest canteens (i.e. 100 seats) have almost eliminated surpluses. Management has certainly become much more careful both in the procurement and in the preparation phases, so only what is necessary for the employees on site on a day-to-day basis is produced in the kitchens. It is today standard for the company canteen to predict the whole daily consumption the day before at the latest.

In large-scale supermarkets in recent years, we have been witnessing a much more aggressive sales method for unsold items, putting products that have reached their minimum shelf life back into commercial circulation, until the last available day. These stocks were previously delivered to non-profits.

Even the production industry in the post-COVID period needed to structure its warehouses differently, planning production with much more accuracy. This reorganization nearly eliminated the availability of perishable products, leaving the non-profit practically only products intended for promotional campaigns once completed. This will continue until companies deem it convenient to repackage those goods and put them back on the market.

Today the entire recovery activity is increasingly difficult, requiring resources certainly higher than it was a few years ago. Some organizations identify two other barriers, one linked to efficiency and one linked to the current legislation.

Coop Lombardia is a remarkable exception to aggressive sales strategy. In recent years they also experimented with a special sale of products close to the expiry date that were offered in specific prime aisles called Last Minute Markets, drastically reduced in price. Although such initiatives followed a request from large chunks of the associates it sold far less than expected. The management decided to cease the Last-Minute Market initiative and re-started donating such food to non-profit organizations. Even if they can provide a purely rational business explanation for choosing donation over sales, the lesson learned by the management was that consumers' (associates in the case of a Cooperative) behavior explains better than dialectic confrontation what customers want.

3.7.5 Economic sustainability

The Local Hub system continuously evaluates (or should) whether a recovery is economically and environmentally convenient even at a smaller scale of catering or small shops. The example is given of a bakery that has 3 kg of surplus bread at the end of the day 3 km away (Interviewee 6). The value of non-waste, added to the use value for the beneficiary, does not offset the costs and environmental impact of transporting and storing the product. Not even the ethical and symbolic value of the recovery is enough to rebalance the deficit. Since there are areas of the city where this type of business is prevalent, it is assumed that a high percentage of the potential recovery for solidarity purposes will not take place. An experience underway in Brescia has created a network of micro realities connected to neighborhood shops that operate this activity in a hyper-delocalized manner. This just works on goods that are available locally and needed locally which intuitively can't cover the bulk of the surplus.

3.7.6 Restrictions on Household Recovery

The legislative level concerns the recovery and redistribution of household food waste, which is the highest percentage in the supply chain. An organization under its responsibility could create a household donation-based food bank but it wouldn't be hygienically compliant, nor protected by the Good Samaritan Law. The organization thus would be accountable for all the consequences of the consumption. It is also predictable that families would donate the most

in concentrated periods (e.g. right before the summer holidays), would deliver close to the expiry date, and most would be poorly labeled to prevent the usage even if considered technically edible. Many organizations think that private food waste is unusable and remains waste. IBVA, one of the Local Hub managers is close to experimenting with the usage of private family food donations to cook food to be distributed in their social markets. As of today, it is unsure if it is legally possible to distribute this type of food to beneficiaries.

3.7.7 Lack of experts and new volunteers

A significant obstacle is related to the demographics of the volunteers. Generational change occurs slowly or not at all. Volunteers in service now began when it was possible to retire at a younger age, still with a desire to continue an active life and plenty of energy to give.

Today people retire much later and dedicate more to rest and recreational activities. This leads to a general decrease in senior expert volunteers.

The most structured organizations are working to involve volunteers who retire from a career in the food sector. The Food Bank for example has acquired many skills from high-level officials and managers of the largest companies in the food sector and this has also enabled it to develop relationships with their former private sector companies.

Youth organizations also have a problem with volunteers, who serve for very limited periods and are inclined to collaborate mainly in the areas of work in which they wish to acquire skills. When only activities that will not cross their interests are needed, they often prefer to give up. Furthermore, in the now globalized labour market, young people find opportunities in different cities or countries much more frequently than in the past, also making their voluntary contribution intermittent.

3.7.8 Expensive cost to keep initiatives sustainable

An important barrier to developing any food hub initiatives is that no sustainability model is independent of public aid or wider networks. In other words, a fully circular, sustainable initiative of food recovery and redistribution is costly, and part of that cost should always be on the collectivity (e.g.: Interviewee 6 and Interviewee 1). If the collectivity receives in return fairer, greener, and equitable communities it should be measurable and quantifiable. This would ease the decision on how, how much, and who should subsidize it. Given that, also financial instruments like social impact bonds would be applicable.

3.8 Changes in policies, behaviours and culture

The decade 2014 – 2024 Opened with the 2015 validation of the UN Agenda 2030 with specific references on SDG-2 **zero hunger**, stating that *food waste and loss throughout the entire value chain is a major problem* and SDG-12 **responsible consumption and production** specifying target 12.3 (By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses) and target 12.5 (By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse).

While the SDGs might look bluntly specific on recovery and redistribution, Milan had a big chance to focus on it when implementing the Expo 2015 *Food for the Planet, Energy for Life* which was a turning point with political, organizational, and legislative impact for the city of Milan and beyond.

Other key events that brought drastic changes were:

The 2020 Circular Economy Package of the European Union

The 2021 approval of the Recovery and Resilience Plan of the EU affects the environment and the food industry.

The 2021 – 2022 COVID-19-related social and economic crisis was very impactful also on the recovery and redistribution initiatives as mentioned previously.

The 2022 – Ongoing Russia-Ukraine conflict with its implications on energy prices and food scarcity as already mentioned.

The City of Milan responded to food emergencies using the experience acquired through the Local Hubs. Using that system as a reference the Food Policy Directorate, the Social Policies Directorate, and the Civil Protection Directorate organized an extraordinarily good aid mechanism covering the whole city in 4 days.

The legacy of the last decade is also a changed social fabric, especially in the urban suburbs. Food poverty doesn't only affect the extremely poor like in the past but also the working poor and the lower-middle class. New targets have different needs therefore require different answers.

3.9 Next Challenges of Food Recovery and Redistribution Initiatives

Some actors think that the way is to **become more capillary** and recover food from always smaller shops that provide quality food in the vicinity. The City of Milan thinks that the way is to leave the micro and **focus on the large**

“there are other ways to reduce waste in small shops, we'll be more efficient recovering food from large supermarkets”.
(Interviewee 1).

providers. This dilemma needs to be addressed since it implies opposite strategies. Foster in all food companies a true commitment. Creating a tangible **reward system** for virtuous companies in example would detach food donations from marketing policies and make them focus on effectiveness.

It is necessary to have an increasingly complete vision of what is happening in the city because *initiatives often travel on parallel tracks that do not intersect*. A systemic and georeferenced vision would allow us to map the areas with unsatisfied needs. To do this the challenge is working together by **sharing systems** and **data**.

As charities are coping with an increase in demand, they refer to nearby supermarkets that are daily submerged with dozens of organizations taking anything in any quantity. The challenge here is to harmonize and include gradually the most possible charities in the redistribution reducing supermarkets interfaces.

3.10 Conflicts

There is a horizontal conflict between non-profit operators. They compete for food donations, public fundings resources and fund raising. The coordination action of the City of Milan tends to rebalance the use of resources and find additional ones to cover more association. While it is possible for this to happen on the topic of food recovery and redistribution, many non-profits operate in various sectors in which they remain competitors. Admittedly there is a latent conflict.

Then there is a vertical conflict with food donor companies. Within the company there are those who develop corporate social responsibility policies prone on delivering food surpluses to non-profit associations, while management control

“My utopian hope is that tomorrow I will no longer have to redistribute the unsold goods but will be able to have a specific financing line to cover all the needs of the poor”.

(Interviewee 6).

and processes engineers create systems to selling until the last possible day, eliminating waste at the origin. Not all companies strive for extreme efficiency and extreme profitability. The case of Coop Lombardia was mentioned previously. Esselunga, a prominent supermarket chain, also chooses to donate most of its food products three days before the expiry date, which is excellent by the Local Hub standards.

To overcome distortions related to competition, the City of Milan used criteria and technicalities to ensure that public fundings were necessarily managed in partnership.

This caused clear difficulties in the dialogue between the organizations in the first round, discrepancies were less accentuated in the second round, and the same actors learned to work together in the third round, even reconciling personal diffidence.

The governance of the Local Hubs system is shared by a group of actors dedicated to the coordination, management, and use of funds. It has been nominated through a memorandum of understanding that links the City of Milan to the Polytechnic of Milan, Assolombarda, and the Cariplo Foundation.

These actors are very relevant, prestigious, and impartial. They have no stake in any of the non-profit operators, so they have no particular interest in influencing food donations, arbitrarily addressing funds, or even in reading the data impartially. This *steering committee* guarantees the good governance and acts as a stabilizer of the entire system.

3.11 Cultural and Social Context

If there is something that represents the spirit of Milan is the phrase *Milan col coeur in man*, Milan with its heart in its hand. It's an old Milanese saying that reminds, mostly the Milanese themselves, that if ever there was a need, the Milanese are generous people. In 1898 *Pane Quotidiano* was founded as a secular, apolitical, and non-profit organization that ensures basic food supplies for everyone in need, every day always for free. *Pane Quotidiano* is part of the Milanese imagery, to signify that whatever happens, one can always find a helping hand.³³

Milan has its local Ethos stemming from its older and more religious traditions. It is linked to the local pride of the Ambrosian Rite, i.e. the doctrine founded by Saint Ambrose in the 4th century. Aurelius Ambrose (Augusta Treverorum, 339-340 – Milan 397) was a Roman official, theologian, and writer, but above all, he was a bishop proclaimed by the people for his capacity to mediate between powers and population. The reference to *Ambrosianism* therefore goes beyond the religious aspect and becomes a way of alluding to the ability to work together in an organized way and to create an equilibrium. Inside you can find values such as rolling up your sleeves, being hardworking, being creative, thinking, and making ethical choices.

Therefore, the generosity and industriousness that the Milanese recognize themselves are at the root of their organizational skills also in the social sector.

The strong religious impulse remains. Many organizations that distribute to the end user are religious and there is a huge network of hundreds of distribution points spread throughout all the neighborhoods of Milan. Every church, every parish, has its own local Caritas equipped with its listening center, social services, and food services.

Thanks to the guarantee of seriousness and reliability of this *last mile of the service to people in need* all other actors of the supply chain gain confidence and operate with serenity³⁴.

3.12 Policy Recommendations

3.12.1 To public administrations:

- Enlarge the action of food recovery to small businesses (i.e., local grocery shops) with ad hoc policies and actions;
- Create a reward system for food-related companies, not only for supermarkets;
- Create a comprehensive and capillary data system that gathers information from different sectors and places;
- Increase the involvement of public administrations in food surplus management and redistribution.
- Design a private donor fundraising scheme to support the entire sector

³³ <https://panequotidiano.eu/>

³⁴ In the food sector, Caritas Ambrosiana distributes 63 thousand food parcels every month at 300 listening centers, recovers 1,600 tonnes of food surpluses per year, and re-introduces them into the solidarity circuit through a solidarity canteen (the Refettorio Ambrosiano), 6 Solidarity Emporiums, 10 communities of hospitality. [Caritas Ambrosiana](#)

3.12.2 To FSIs:

- Improve the dialogue with other FSIs and create networks;
- Overcome competition for joint efforts in applying funds and reaching resources;
- Improve communication and local presence;
- Create an alternative approach to volunteer recruitment

3.12.3 To the private sector

- Create a common policy to coordinate food donation (i.e., similar expiration date, efficiency to waste reduction, and food typology);
- Harmonize the dialogue with non-profit organizations and administrations.
- Comply with State and City incentives on food waste

3.13 Conclusions

This report considers the main initiatives emerging from the citywide networks of local hubs against food waste, MUFPP policy brief, Milan Food Policy reports, the interviews with Interviewee 1 (City of Milan), Interviewee 2 (City of Milan), Interviewee 3 (Politecnico di Milano), Interviewee 4 (Coop Lombardia), Interviewee 6 (IBVA), Interviewee 7 (Banco Alimentare della Lombardia), in January and February 2024. The research centered around the latest urban policies implemented in the domain of Food Waste Recovery in which the City of Milan is directly involved as well as other relevant networks. Using Cultivate project research action as a third-party observation point allowed participants from the City of Milan, Non-profit organizations, and the University to provide independent unbiased information and opinions. This helped to draft a more accurate description of barriers and also envisage enablers to leverage.

Even if Milan could count on the hundreds of independent initiatives on food waste and recovery, two main factors (Expo 2015 and the Covid-related social and economic crisis) pushed the City administration to step into a sector originally outside its domain to optimize resources, circulate knowledge and converge interests of many different stakeholders. The City of Milan has provided a safe space for co-competition between NGOs, Companies, Universities, and civil society where potentially everyone wins, the bottom line being vulnerable people with more food available and the environment with less food wasted. Of course, it came at a *taxpayers'* cost, as this setting depends on the political will, and a change in the political scenario may lead to a different outcome. There isn't counterfactual evidence that the system wouldn't be operating without the current level of City coordination. On the other hand, the current network of participants is satisfied and a growing number of organizations applied to join the scheme in the 2023 public manifestation of interest. This all converges on the necessity of an increasingly specific, accurate, and transparent culture of accountability that provides policymakers and citizens with a neat picture.

This seems to be a key point in the short term as food companies, supermarket chains, retailers, NGOs, charities, civil society organizations, public administration departments, and Universities are often reluctant to collect, analyse and share their data.

In the long term, bigger innovations might be needed to confront drastic changes that may occur like a decrease in the available food supply, a lack of volunteers, or a change on the demand side only to name a few. Only a strong alliance among stakeholders would be able to ease the slow and complex bureaucracy, challenge some legal boundaries, and raise the funds necessary to envisage and achieve creative solutions for the food waste and redistribution sector in the years to come.

4. Social Solidarity Economy

4.1 Introduction

Food sharing involves collective actions around food and food-related items, spaces, skills, and knowledge. It can take place between friends, families, neighbours, communities, and strangers across the food systems from growing cooking and eating to surplus food redistribution. CULTIVATE focuses on food sharing beyond friends and family, and specifically on initiatives explicitly set up to share food.

Food sharing is a foundational human behaviour, and the City of Milan has an acknowledged good practice stemming from the dozens of secular and faith-based community kitchens scattered around the city, often supported by the long-term established Regional Food Bank.

The CULTIVATE project's latest field research, which concluded in January 2024, assessed more than 100 Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) in the city of Milan, shaping the backbone of the food-related Social and Solidarity Economy (SSE).

Food-related SSE is a response to food poverty and, being closely connected to general poverty, can also be tackled with active labour policies that tend to make economically independent those vulnerable groups that are currently subsidized. Passive labour policy (Universal income above all) and active labour policy competencies are split over a multitude of entities and stakeholders whose interests and objectives are often uncoordinated and sometimes collide.

Nevertheless, cities are incredible levers of change and specifically of solidarity responses to food poverty. Skills, resources, infrastructures, knowledge, and relationships are concentrated in cities more than in any other territory or institution.

Regional, national, or supranational bodies can activate general and long-term levers, but cities combine the regulatory and policy dimensions with the *maker factor* which in the case of food aid policies transpose into real examples of SSE.

The Food Policy in Milan for example, encompassing both the regulatory and administrative dynamics, has managed to shape a pilot programme and make it effective in a short period of time. The next step is to take the food poverty initiatives out of emergency status and make it a strategic priority. Indeed, this entails an open admission that the problem itself is a structural social condition.

Many Cities are consolidating dedicated departments, which can be the point of reference for city-scale SSE actions. In Milan the competent structures on an urban scale combine the mandates of food policy with those of agriculture and food poverty, effectively becoming the centre of governance for a wider system.

Such governance is tentatively inclusive because it entails permanent tables for dialogue and discussion with stakeholders, but it is also competent, managing to dialogue with knowledge of the facts on multiple topics with all system actors up to the individual citizen.

4.2 Regulatory frameworks and Policies

There are several layers of strategies, policies, laws, and regulations affecting FSIs in Milan. In the context of SSE, as well as Food Waste Recovery and Redistribution (FWR), it is possible to congregate on Global, European, Italian, Regional, and Urban scales. Most of the regulatory acts mentioned in the FWR report are generally relevant for SSE (**Good Samaritan Law** L. 155/2003³⁵, The **Gadda Law** L. 166/2016³⁶, The **Law 35/2015 Recognition, Protection, and Promotion of the Right to food**³⁷, The **Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point** (HACCP) system³⁸, The **Milan Urban Food Policy Pact** (MUFPP)³⁹, and The **Milan Food Policy** City of Milan Resolution 25/2015⁴⁰.

The **Gadda Law** L. 166/2016 whose partial application has been described in the FWR report is seen as focused mainly on waste reduction without a direct impact on food poverty alleviation. Some organizations think that food producers could be incentivized even more by creating a tax deduction scheme for companies programming an overproduction of quality food specifically destined for food aid recipients. Such a scheme would allow for coordinating, programming, and distributing nutritious and quality food as required.

Some other regulations are more specifically correlated to SSE:

- **FEAD 2021-27**
- **European Child Guarantee**
- **Codice del Terzo Settore L. 117/2017**
- **5 x 1000**

FEAD 2021-27. The European Commission and the Italian Ministry of Labour and Social

Policies authorised the Operational Program relating to the Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived (FEAD) to implement a series of interventions on the national territory in favour of people in conditions of serious material deprivation.

In Italy, FEAD mainly finances the purchase and distribution of food, goods and, to a lesser extent, the supply of school materials to children belonging to disadvantaged families, the activation of school canteens in territorial areas with strong socio-economic disadvantages, aid for homeless people and those in extremely marginalized conditions.

The purchase and distribution of food are implemented through the Agency for Agricultural Disbursements (AGEA), as an intermediate body, with whom the Ministry has stipulated a specific agreement, also defining the basket of food products to be distributed. The national lead partner

³⁵LEGGE 25 giugno 2003, n. 155 Disciplina della distribuzione dei prodotti alimentari a fini di solidarieta' sociale. (GU Serie Generale n.150 del 01-07-2003)

³⁶ LEGGE 19 agosto 2016, n. 166 Disposizioni concernenti la donazione e la distribuzione di prodotti alimentari e farmaceutici a fini di solidarieta' sociale e per la limitazione degli sprechi. (16G00179) (GU Serie Generale n.202 del 30-08-2016)

³⁷ Legge Regionale 6 novembre 2015 , n. 34 Legge di riconoscimento, tutela e promozione del diritto al cibo (BURL n. 46, suppl. del 10 Novembre 2015)

³⁸ Decreto Legislativo 26 maggio 1997, n. 155 "Attuazione delle direttive 93/43/CEE e 96/3/CE concernenti l'igiene dei prodotti alimentari" (Gazzetta Ufficiale n. 136 del 13 giugno 1997 - Supplemento Ordinario n. 118)

³⁹ Gabinetto del sindaco deliberazione n° 25 del 5/10/2015 (Verbale di deliberazione del Consiglio Comunale)

⁴⁰ Linee di indirizzo della Food Policy di Milano

organisations already accredited by AGEA can therefore access the program and in turn distribute it to all the local actors belonging to their networks.

The FEAD support is considered a pillar of SSE, and its consistency and continuity guaranteed a capillary distribution of food aid in the city of Milan. Some organizations argue that the basket of available products is limited and needs to be complemented with more nutritious food to help families. A solidarity supermarket manager pointed out that FEAD/AGEA products are frugally packaged so that they look poor on the shelf and create a second-class feel to the shop and a sense of deprivation to clients.

European Child Guarantee. In 2019 a European Child Guarantee was created to ensure that every child in Europe at risk of poverty or social exclusion has access to the most basic of rights like healthcare, education, and a set of key services:

- free early childhood education and care
- free education (including school-based activities and at least one healthy meal each school day)
- free healthcare
- healthy nutrition
- adequate housing

The European Child Guarantee Action Plan in Italy strengthens and re-thinks the management of food poverty funds, through the constitution of a National Food Solidarity Fund with adequate resources to ensure a more equitable distribution among municipalities, through a better balance between the criterion of population and income. Coordination of European resources for food poverty, PON, and European Social Fund (ESF), the use of funds for school canteens and support for local authorities, in full respect of the principle of subsidiarity and using multi-actor intervention, to provide the following:

- More flexible and effective access criteria and complementary measures (including those involving associations and third sector entities, mutual help groups, and neighbourhood associations) capable of intercepting all families in need, especially those with child dependents.
- Guaranteed free access to the school canteen for all families. Eliminate, where present, any reference to the criteria of residence and/or citizenship as a requisite for access to measures to combat food poverty. In the personalized projects for taking charge of the RdC, specific accompanying actions that take into consideration the issue of food quality and proper nutrition for children.
- Strategies to combat food poverty coordinated among the various local authorities, for example by including them in the Area Plans.
- Support the innovation of food assistance models, for example through the creation of 'solidarity pacts' with local food actors to strengthen local food systems and establish food assistance supply chains (for example, using supermarket surpluses) to run alongside traditional food supply channels.
- The adoption of rights-based food policies that consider children and include effective strategies to combat food poverty and promote the effective participation of all actors in the

food system at the municipal and metropolitan levels, enhancing the role of civic networks and organized civil society.

- The encouragement of greater participation and empowerment of programme beneficiary groups.
- The promotion of food education programmes, not only in schools, but also in families, to promote awareness of healthy and sustainable diets.
- The integration of policies to combat food poverty with local health policies. In this regard, it is useful to facilitate the interception of vulnerable cases through the use of territorial health centres (for example, pharmacies, counselling centres, community houses).
- Adopt a strategy to combat food poverty, clear objectives, strategies and indicators should be defined to guide policies at the national and territorial levels.

These strategies should consider the specificities of the target group of children and the adoption of the Child Guarantee.

Legge 117/2017. The Italian Law 117/2017, also known as the *Codice del Terzo Settore* or Code of the Third Sector, is a significant piece of legislation that regulates and promotes the activities of nonprofit organisations, volunteering, and social enterprises in Italy. It was enacted on 3 August 2017 and came into effect on 1 January 2018. The law aims to provide a comprehensive legal framework to support the development and sustainability of the third sector, which encompasses a wide range of organizations and initiatives that operate for social, cultural, philanthropic, and environmental purposes, rather than for profit. This longtime expected law represents a legal framework whose primary aspects are:

- the definition of the entire third sector
- the recognition of various legal forms for third-sector organisations (including associations, foundations, social cooperatives, and other types of entities) providing specific regulations for each type of organisation (including governance structures, reporting requirements, and fiscal incentives)
- the establishment of provisions for volunteering, recognizing the importance of volunteer work in contributing to social cohesion and solidarity. It defines volunteering activities, rights, and protections for volunteers, and encourages the involvement of volunteers in various social initiatives.
- the promotion of social enterprises, which are businesses that pursue social or environmental objectives while generating revenue. It introduces specific regulations for social enterprises, including criteria for certification and incentives to support their growth and impact.
- the provision of fiscal incentives and tax benefits for third-sector organisations and donors, including tax deductions for donations and contributions to non-profit entities. These incentives aim to encourage philanthropy and support the sustainability of thirdsector activities.
- the emphasis on transparency and accountability in the operations of third-sector organisations, requiring them to adopt clear governance structures, disclose financial information, and adhere to reporting standards. It aims to enhance public trust and confidence in the sector.

Overall, the *Codice del Terzo Settore* represents a significant step towards strengthening the legal and institutional framework for the third sector in Italy, fostering its growth, innovation, and impact in addressing social challenges and promoting the common good.

The relevance of the *Codice del Terzo Settore* for organisations that alleviate food poverty is significant in terms of:

- **Recognition and Support:** The law acknowledges the importance of addressing food poverty and related issues within the third sector. By providing a legal framework that supports and regulates nonprofit organizations, the Codice del Terzo Settore facilitates the establishment and operation of entities specifically dedicated to alleviating food poverty.
- **Funding and Resources:** Third-sector organizations working to alleviate food poverty often rely on funding and resources to carry out their activities, such as food distribution, meal programs, and education initiatives. The legislation provides fiscal incentives and tax benefits that can attract donations and contributions from individuals, businesses, and other organizations, thereby increasing the financial resources available to support anti-poverty efforts.
- **Volunteer Engagement:** Volunteerism is a crucial aspect of many initiatives aimed at alleviating food poverty. The Codice del Terzo Settore includes provisions for volunteering, recognizing the essential role of volunteers in supporting communitybased initiatives, including food distribution programs, community kitchens, and food banks. By formalizing the rights and protections of volunteers, the law encourages their involvement in these activities.
- **Social Enterprises:** Some organizations addressing food poverty may operate as social enterprises, combining their social mission with sustainable business models. The legislation promotes the development of social enterprises and provides specific regulations and incentives to support their growth and impact. This can enable organizations focused on food poverty to explore innovative approaches to sustainability while fulfilling their mission.
- **Transparency and Accountability:** Transparency and accountability are crucial for organizations working in the field of food poverty to build trust with donors, volunteers, and the community. The Codice del Terzo Settore emphasizes these principles, requiring organizations to adhere to reporting standards, disclose financial information, and maintain clear governance structures. By promoting transparency and accountability, the law enhances the credibility and effectiveness of anti-poverty initiatives.

Overall, the *Codice del Terzo Settore* offers a supportive and enabling environment for organizations dedicated to alleviating food poverty, providing them with legal recognition, funding opportunities, volunteer engagement mechanisms, and regulatory frameworks that can enhance their impact and sustainability in addressing this critical social issue.

4.3 Funding the initiatives

5x1000. The "5x1000" is a mechanism that allows taxpayers in Italy to allocate a portion of their income tax (IRPEF) to eligible non-profit organizations (NPOs) or voluntary organizations. The mechanism includes:

"community kitchen clients are often at the margins of marginality"
(Interviewee 1).

- **Allocation:** Italian taxpayers have the option to allocate 0.5% of their annual income tax to either the state, a specific non-profit organization, or both. This allocation does not involve any additional cost to the taxpayer; rather, it comes from the overall amount of income tax they owe.
- **Eligible Organisations:** The organisations eligible to receive donations through the 5x1000 mechanism include various types of non-profit organizations, such as charities, social cooperatives, cultural associations, and religious institutions. These organisations must be recognised by the Italian tax authorities (Agenzia delle Entrate) and meet specific criteria to qualify for the allocation.
- **Declaration:** To participate in the 5x1000 program, taxpayers must indicate their preference on their annual income tax return (Modello 730 or Unico). Specifically, they need to fill in the appropriate section of the tax return form, selecting either the option to allocate 0.5% of their tax to the state, a specific NPO, or both. Taxpayers can choose to support a different organisation each year or maintain their allocation to the same organisation.
- **Transparency and Oversight:** The Italian tax authorities oversee the allocation of funds through the 5x1000 mechanism to ensure transparency and accountability. They verify the eligibility of participating organizations and monitor the proper allocation of funds according to taxpayers' preferences.
- **Impact:** The funds raised through the 5x1000 mechanism can have a significant impact on the activities and projects of eligible non-profit organizations. These funds may support a wide range of initiatives, including social services, healthcare programs, educational projects, environmental conservation efforts, cultural activities, and more.

Overall, the 5x1000 program provides taxpayers in Italy with an opportunity to contribute to the support of non-profit organizations and initiatives that align with their values and interests. By participating in this program, taxpayers can make a positive impact on their communities and society as a whole, leveraging a portion of their income tax for charitable purposes.

Most of the organizations implementing food-related SSE programmes in Milan can count on the massive contribution of volunteers, can connect with crowds of individual donors, and have access to corporate clients. This social capital is the perfect condition for the 5x1000 fundraising device to succeed.

4.4 Different models of solidary social economy

Food-related initiatives in the field of social solidarity economy in Milan generally refer to the distribution of food resources without monetary exchange or taxation, therefore food aid involves

the collaboration of *food agents* and *deprived populations*. Symbolically, the collective imagery goes to the distribution of parcels to families even if the city of Milan is rich in initiatives and solidarity economy ideas. **Four prevalent models** are present throughout the city responding to different targets of citizens.

The **first model** is the **community kitchen** (in Italian *mensa solidale*). **There are nine in Milan**, all managed by faith-based organizations, on church-owned premises and providing ready meals to homeless and seriously marginalized people. They cover approximately the needs of **9500 people daily** (see Interviewee 1 interview). These people are often chronically marginalized and sometimes out of reach for social services. Most of the operators refer to them as those who do not want to be helped in a structured way so that they might die on the street when not able to eat regularly. Even in these desperate conditions, they have learned to use the community kitchen food services. A variation of this model is the mobile kitchen developed mainly by Croce Rossa e Progetto Arca which is a food truck visiting the places where the homeless typically settle overnight.

The **second model**, prevalent in Milan, is the **distribution of food aid** in the form of food boxes organized by help centers, parishes, and community houses. There are **around 193** throughout the city of Milan and are supplied by the FEAD Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived, through the recovery and redistribution of food surpluses, or donations and purchases made by the charity organizations themselves⁴¹. In this case, the target group is generally represented by a family unit, and the delivery is meant to integrate the food needed by the family both qualitatively and quantitatively.

The **third model** is the **solidarity market**, which consists of premises organized in the same way as a commercial supermarket and provides authorized users with a choice of food and non-food products. There are about **6 places** like this in Milan. They target families who are provided with a personal user card loaded with *points* that equal credits to be used at the till instead of real money (some markets ask for a symbolic contribution to grow users' engagement). Each item exposed on the shelves is labeled with its worth in points. The points per item (unit value) are calculated by both the scarcity and the market value of each item. The *points* (credit) are loaded monthly on the user cards depending on the financial situation of the family, the number of members, the presence of minors, and other categories. The solidarity card model provides a more proactive experience to users leveraging on their responsibility in the use of personal and familial resources. It is also very dignifying because it tends to fill a temporary need (or make users feel so), because in most of the solidarity markets it encourages a turnover of clients after approximately six months. Of course, an extension is granted when needed, but the idea is to escort families toward their full financial independence. Goods are generally coming from the FEAD Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived, the local food banks, the city hubs, local donations, and sometimes from purchases.

The fourth category is that of the **food voucher**, which is also mainly intended for families to deal with temporary situations of poverty. It is a tool that in Milan was managed directly by the Municipal Administration. The Municipality of Milan activated several **tens of thousands** of them during the pandemic emergency and renewed the measure several times afterwards. It is a measure funded by the national government and is activated by the municipalities every time the national

⁴¹ Milano aiuta. Un pasto per tutti. City of Milan 2022

government confirms the financing. The food voucher is a direct measure that puts the public administration in contact with every single beneficiary without intermediation, unlike the three previous models in which the relationship with the user was delegated to civil society organizations.

The relationship between all entities occurs mainly through the source of food supply. Almost all these initiatives are affiliated with the circuit of the **FEAD** which is managed by **AGEA** and therefore falls within the competencies of the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies. In Italy, the FEAD mechanism authorizes a few lead organizations, equipped with warehouses and logistics platforms that receive the foodstuffs determined at the European level and which are in turn connected to a circuit of territorial partners to which they deliver products based on the number of beneficiaries they care for. These entities consequently all enter the FEAD system.

The Municipality of Milan has launched a complementary **food aid service** which expanded the range of products for the organizations in the FEAD system within the city of Milan. This is granted through a public tender and a subsequent selection. The subjects adhering to this circuit are then in turn coordinated by the Food Policy area of the Municipality of Milan which in various capacities interacts with and facilitates relationships between these subjects.

There are **3 lead organizations** in Milan, local branches of national organizations. They are the **Food Bank** (Banco Alimentare della Lombardia), the **Italian Red Cross** (Croce Rossa Italiana – Comitato della Lombardia), and **Caritas** (Caritas Ambrosiana). Among them, there is a prevailing actor which is the Food Bank, which serves around 130 partner organizations, followed by the Italian Red Cross, which serves around 60. These 190 entities are those that generally deliver food boxes (in some cases even at beneficiaries' premises). Caritas Ambrosiana has mainly associated solidarity emporiums and solidarity markets in its network.

QuBì is the program against child poverty promoted by the Cariplo Foundation with the support of the Peppino Vismara Foundation, Intesa Sanpaolo, the Romeo and Enrica Invernizzi Foundation, the Fiera Milano Foundation, and the Snam Foundation and active in the city of Milan since 2017. The objective of the Program is to combat the phenomenon of child poverty by promoting collaboration between public institutions and the third sector and carrying out interventions aimed at specific needs in 25 neighbourhoods of the city of Milan. There are four main axes of action⁴²:

- Carry out a constantly updated analysis of absolute poverty in Milan.
- Increase access to spending for families in economic difficulty.
- Promote integrated systems for taking care of beneficiaries.
- Carry out specific and innovative actions to combat food poverty.

The actions see the direct and indirect involvement of various operational partners, in addition to the Municipality of Milan, in particular: Caritas Ambrosiana, Banco Alimentare della Lombardia, IBVA Solidando, Fondazione di Comunità Milano. Since the pandemic the focus shifted from educational poverty to food poverty and partners were allowed to use the programme's financial resources for this purpose.

⁴² QUBÌ. [Ricetta Contro La Povertà Infantile.](#)

4.5 Governance Landscape

The City of Milan food aid service is a policy tool to guarantee a significant supply of food aid to the deprived. For this social solidarity economy program, the City of Milan activated the networks previously consolidated with the Local Hubs against the food waste program (see previous report on FWR), leveraging on the knowledge and mutual trust within the communities of practice. There is a specific community of practice on food aid, therefore a fullfledged social solidarity economy practice, which is constantly updated. The program dates to the emergency linked to the pandemic, when the food aid distribution system went into crisis because many of the elderly volunteers who were the reference target for the distribution of food aid were also the main target of the virus. As a result, the organizations suspended recovery and distribution activities as a precaution. And in this way, the City of Milan entered the front line by activating a food aid service that mobilized its employees. In all, **82 employees** participated in the food support operations, in **10 spaces** which are usually public centres for the elderly that were temporarily closed. Thanks to the exceptional use of people and places, the municipality managed a centralized logistics system usually used by the Food Bank. The supply chain usually guaranteed by Food Bank and Red Cross was managed by civil servants and equipped vans usually in school service were adapted. The City of Milan readapted some of the existing schemes with its people and equipment creating a subsidiary system with **2 logistics centres** to collect extraordinary donations and purchase food and **10 distribution centres** to reach families at their premises⁴³.

Public funds for the procurement of the transport of disabled people were diverted into funds for the provision of services for food delivery.

This action lasted throughout the first lockdown, about four months until June 2020. Since the autumn of 2020, the City of Milan has tried to make this measure structural. Since then, the Municipality has budgeted €700,000 per year for the sole purpose of directly financing the purchase of food by organizations which, after the pandemic, have returned to carrying out the service.

The municipality of Milan initially selected **8 managing Organizations**, which have been subsequently renewed annually. This means the capacity to buy food continuously to supply people in need to complement the food that was already recovered as a surplus from companies.

The lessons learned during the pandemic allowed the administration to accelerate the creation of a governance for the food related SSE policy which was subsequently stabilized.

It is described as an unplanned action, developed through **learning by doing** with the experience gained rapidly in the four months of the first policy tool when the City of Milan directly managed the entire operations including the identification of needs, the food purchases, the logistics and the delivery to beneficiaries.

*“The City of Milan departments, Social policy and Food Policy become coordinators that still lead jointly”
(Interviewee 2).*

⁴³ Milano aiuta. Un pasto per tutti. City of Milan 2022

A trial-and-error period contributed to consolidating findings that helped to shape the current governance. The legacy included:

- The City of Milan and the 82 employees involved became field experts in functions that were not typically within their competences.
- The City of Milan has raised awareness among a significant portion of public employees regarding the problem of food poverty (many civil servants remained volunteers even after the end of the emergency)
- The City of Milan has practiced direct functions linked to food aid processes which have become crucial in co-designing other policy tools in dialogue with third sector organizations.
- The Food Policy and Social Policy sectors continued the collaboration even after the end of the emergency.
- Local networks linked to FEAD functioned as platforms to co-design complementary services.
- Other non-profit organizations outside the FEAD network entered the SSE network of the City of Milan (the only condition was to have a warehouse at their disposal).
- A funding scheme solely dedicated to the purchase of food commodities was designed.
- Interventions specifically focused on food poverty facilitated measuring the general impact.

Other elements make this experience unique, and it has brought many positive effects and externalities to Milan.

4.5.1 Simplifying bureaucracy through an exemption process.

The City of Milan reacted very quickly immediately after the launch of the **national emergency decree** of 16 March 2020. The government published a **civil protection ordinance** that allowed municipal administrations, in derogation of any legislation, to purchase and distribute food, besides providing the financial allowance to do so⁴⁴.

The City of Milan had started with its initiative a few weeks earlier and was in fact ready to deploy. Having funds available and having legal protection allowed the City to operate quickly enough for recipients to have the food they needed in 4 weeks instead of 2 months with standard procedures. 700,000 euros of the government's 7 million euros were spent to purchase food starting from the fourth week and distributed through the system of 10 temporary Hubs already set up in the first four weeks⁴⁵. This exceptional situation created a precedent so that the City of Milan could react with a proven procedure in case of future calamities. These exceptional results obtained in response to an emergency can become a standard operational procedure even for more structural problems.

4.5.2 Making financial resources adaptable

Some organizations reported that the use of funds was exceptionally flexible. There are cases where they succeeded in managing a peak in demand related to the Ukrainian refugee inflow simply by asking and obtaining an anticipation from the City of Milan. On the other hand, it is reported that in the presence of slow spending at the end of the fiscal year, an organization asked and obtained to use the unspent budget to stock up for the forthcoming year. This flexibility in the use of funding is

⁴⁴ Ordinanza 27 febbraio 2020 *Ulteriori interventi urgenti di protezione civile in relazione all'emergenza relativa al rischio sanitario connesso all'insorgenza di patologie derivanti da agenti virali trasmissibili.* (Ordinanza n. 640). (20A01348) (GU Serie Generale n.50 del 28-02-2020)

⁴⁵ Milano aiuta. [Al via l'avviso pubblico per un nuovo dispositivo di aiuto alimentare.](#) 16/11/2020

considered essential for food-related aid and is the perfect complement to food recovery and redistribution which is always difficult to program.

4.5.3 Experimenting with a dual system.

Many food companies continued to produce surplus and wanted to donate it, while some other foods were in short supply even for purchase. Having two capable and competent organizations in the network allowed the City of Milan to activate two distinct channels with:

- The Red Cross was exclusively dedicated to purchasing the missing foodstuffs by releasing government funds.
- The Food Bank was dedicated to collecting surpluses. Donations arrived from many companies including Parmalat, Galbani, Bolton, Save the Children, NaturaSì, Lidl and others.

4.5.4 Expanding visibility

The mayor himself encouraged the city effort in the first weeks taking part in some kick-off actions making the Policy tool more visible. City officers needed to be engaged, non-profit organizations needed to be motivated and citizens needed to be reassured.

4.5.5 Enhancing cooperation

The City of Milan departments broke their *silos walls* and cooperated more than diligently. The departments of Mobility, Food policy, and Social policy, plus publicly owned companies like AMAT (who designed the logistics plans for the Hubs), Milano

“Some of the emerging issues were resolved within a couple of hours, before Covid, this would have taken days”
(Interviewee 1)

Ristorazione (provided and paid for the transports) and Sogemi (opened the wholesale market doors to recover 138 tons of fresh fruits and vegetables fruit and vegetables and 50,000 kits of. preserved produce) were the backbones of the policy tool. Even if the period was painful, the emergency response is remembered in the City of Milan positively. So both, the regulatory exemptions and the spontaneous collaboration made this initiative valuable.

4.6 Motivations behind food sharing

Food poverty not only means providing (relatively) cheap conserved food that can easily filter down from the FEAD/AGEA program to small charities through authorized national NGOs. It also means complementing food aids with nutritious and fresh produce, which is more valuable, even if more difficult to obtain. This only can be achieved through a stable, organized collaboration with multiple local stakeholders.

For NGOs collaboration also means access to funds. The City of Milan is managing the whole of the National aid programme and decided to deploy it after a co-designing process in close collaboration with implementing organizations. This entails the organization’s availability to collaborating with the City of Milan and with other organizations to integrate the operations and cover the whole city. Coordination meetings and communities of practice became the standard collaboration means.

The collaboration of local authorities with the NGOs though is mainly motivated by a common feeling of being part of the change. Both in the more formal and informal moments of exchange, the people who participated always reported an almost ideal adhesion to the initiative. The desire

“Our (IBVA) relationship with the city administration is very easy as they simplified the bureaucracy and we can access the decision makers at any time”

(Interviewee 6)

that the result of one's actions was a truly collective benefit. During the pandemic, the economic resources to guarantee home transport ran out and the coordinating office invited beneficiaries to contact the “local Hubs directly with a booking system via text message. This meant that the employees of the City of Milan and the volunteers interacted with the entire target group of beneficiaries. So, everyone who went personally to collect in the very early morning had a direct relationship with a city officer. The City of Milan recognizes that experience as transformative, that is, capable of changing the perception of employees from bureaucrats to true civil servants. In most cases, the people involved referred to themselves on this occasion as "part of the change".

It is very important to remember that the public employees who participated in the initiative did so voluntarily. In fact, in those days all common work suspended in-person activities, switching to smart working. The City of Milan thus launched a public call for membership in the task force called Milano Help (Milano Aiuta) in which employees from all sectors could participate. Over 200 people applied from 21 different departments, among which, as specified above, 82 took up service. On other occasions, other criteria have been used, from alphabetical order to coercion, but on this occasion the call was free and voluntary, showing that the only motivation was the sense of responsibility and the desire to seize the opportunity to feel part of the change.

4.7 Storytelling of Solidary Social Economy

In the context of the SSE, the vision of the support network is almost uniform. Food is a human right and the fight against food poverty is everyone's mission. Pursuing this result unites all operators. Some offer their logistical skills, others are more social or humanitarian or aimed at children, resulting in different approaches.

From the point of view of the recipients, the front of the organizations that take action to provide food aid is united. There are no visible divergent narratives. There are operational differences between those who distribute the product to everyone, like Pane Quotidiano and Emergency, who didn't request identification or to classify the beneficiaries. There are religious organizations that often distribute aid to people of all religious beliefs. Other organizations rely on a more rigorous census of beneficiaries, verifying and classifying their specific state of need.

If the core of the narrative is almost uniform, the messages that organizations spread during fundraising campaigns are very different. Voluntary associations compete in raising funds to carry out their activities, especially ordinary ones. In this sense, the fundraising campaigns aimed at individual donors are those that leverage the so-called 5x1000. This measure is very popular among voluntary organizations that **launch their campaigns all at the same time** of the year close to the

tax deadlines of individual contributors. this is where the messages tend to differ by pointing to emotional rather than rational elements.

From the public at large point of view, different programs tell different stories. Community kitchens that have been operating for centuries testify that **poor people will always exist**, and cities need compassion and solidarity from their citizens to help them. The distribution of food aid in food boxes shows that **food poverty can be temporary** and with a push families can get back on their feet. The solidarity markets make us aware that **being a consumer makes everyone feel part of the community**. The food voucher reminds us that we can safely **choose quality over quantity** and our health doesn't always depend on our spending capacity but also on our habits.

The weakest pattern of communication is the connections between food aid SSE and environmental impact. In the case of FWR, the impact of waste prevention is well explicated, whereas in the case of SSE a systematic assessment of food waste is still unavailable.

4.8 Main Enablers of Solidary Social Economy

4.8.1 National Funds in the Next Years

The Government has kept food aid funding as an emergency measure, and this is a barrier to the food-related SSE capacity to plan and invest accordingly. On the other hand, the Italian Government is the EU's biggest spender distributing some €500,000,000 yearly to Italian cities.

4.8.2 Development of a comprehensive control room

An enabling factor for SSE policies related to food is having a **control room** capable of involving stakeholders and constantly communicating with them. The City of Milan implemented a European project which concluded two years ago as part of the Urbact programme linked to corporate social responsibility. Within that project, tools were developed to build synergistic actions of public-private partnerships together with businesses. Food policy was one of the departments of the City involved precisely because over the years it has consolidated more **familiarity with profit companies** compared to other departments. Starting from the fact that elements of sustainability for the SSE derive from the ability to structure private-public partnerships, the City of Milan explored the topic of what the enabling elements were for consolidating this type of policy. It emerged that an enabling element is certainly effective communication and a change of narrative. The winning representation is that of a public body as an entity open to joint initiatives, competent beyond the mere role of relationship facilitator, an entity that co-plans openly and transparently involving all stakeholders. Calls for tenders, sponsorships, technical sponsorships, and patronages are agile tools for capturing resources of various types and placing them in the same container.

4.8.3 Matching function between local needs and companies

Another enabling factor, in addition to the funding mix, is the **matching function** between local needs and company resources. Public coordination ensures that companies interested in operating in a neighborhood are also made aware of the social needs of that neighborhood, starting to imagine solutions even to needs that cannot strictly be addressed through a commercial relationship. Funds, unused spaces, tools, technologies, means of communication, means of transport of companies can become resources at the service of the territory focused on fighting food poverty. With this system,

the City of Milan has already pooled the resources of professional football clubs and utility companies with others apparently far from the food aid system.

4.8.4 Overcome single donation approach

The logic is to overcome the single donation, the philanthropic approach or the marketing logics that underlie corporate social responsibility. The objective is to build lasting relationships and develop the ability to **design solutions together** with all the actors involved. This is how the system will become more and more compact and cohesive.

4.8.5 The Municipality is promoting collaborative initiatives

There are policies governed and coordinated by the City of Milan which have a consolidated core of main actors who are those who have signed the agreements and are also recipients of public subsidies. Most of the actors are also connected to FWR policies and represent the last mile, the transmission line with the final recipients, acquiring

“When the public administration is promoting collaborative initiatives, in a way it guarantees a dynamic and correct collaboration and this counts”

(Interviewee 5)

great importance in this sense. The **understanding of needs** and the **codesigning of systemic responses** begins with SSE operators. The connection with the city-wide policy allows small, volunteer-based organizations to elevate their efficiency and guarantee a quality service for their beneficiaries. Still, many informal or temporary initiatives won't accept to coordinate formally.

4.8.6 Consolidated relationships between public, private and third-sector entities

The link between the City of Milan and the affiliated entities is expressed through a relationship of collaboration, trust, shared methodologies, and common language which ensures that, when faced with new problems or shared challenges, these entities are the first to develop a common dialogue. This is why these actors are the ones best able to influence the development of SSE food policy.

4.9 Main Barriers to Solidary Social Economy

4.9.1 Lack of funds

One of the biggest barriers is related to **financing**. The major public investments have been made since the pandemic and have increased year on year. The paradox is that, even if it is recognized that the problem of food poverty has become structural (even in 2023 the number of people in a state of absolute poverty in Italy has increased⁴⁶) the organized response is still an emergency. One of the systematic responses that the City of Milan with its main stakeholders is trying to organize is to create a funding mix in which, alongside public funding, funds from companies and private individuals also come in. This would give greater consistency to the bottom and consequently greater stability. Moreover, it is also suggested that taxpayers' funds can also be collected locally using the Milan City budget to cover Milan's food aid service.

⁴⁶ ISTAT. [Economia 25/03/2024](#).

3.9.2 Decrease in volunteers

The other major obstacle, as in the case of the FWR is the **decrease in volunteers**. The people who typically dedicate themselves to food aid tend to be elderly and/or retired and year after year this population is dwindling. Generational change is problematic both because young people wish to participate in voluntary activities that are closer to their interests and functional to their careers, and because the retirement age is getting longer and longer, and because many pensioners need to use their time for small jobs and paid activities.

4.9.3 Food Shortages and Capacity to Provide Valuable Food

One further obstacle is related to the **capacity of organizations to provide valuable food**. The volunteer shortage here connects with the specific limitations that food provisions require. In the case of waste from supermarkets both conserved food, delivered only on specific days and times, and fresh food that needs specific equipment and human competences, make this type of food collection a bit limiting.

4.9.4 Competition among operators and initiatives

One last obstacle is the **competition among operators** (NGOs, CSOs, Associations, etc...). They compete for food provisions, funding, volunteers, and support networks. This is where coordination and leadership are needed. The only institution that can guarantee a fair, unbiased, and effective governance is the public administration. This is why the City of Milan's Food Policy rapidly gained relevance and regard.

4.10 Changes in policies and social contexts

The decade 2014 – 2024 Opened with the 2015 validation of the UN Agenda 2030 with specific references on SDG-2 **zero hunger** aimed at ending hunger, achieving food security and improved nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture. FSIs can surely contribute to it at a scale.

While the SDGs might look bluntly specific on recovery and redistribution, Milan had a big chance to focus on it when implementing the Expo 2015 *Food for the Planet, Energy for Life* which was a turning point with political, organizational, and legislative impact for the city of Milan and beyond.

Other key events that brought drastic changes were:

- The 2020 Circular Economy Package of the European Union
- The 2021 approval of the Recovery and Resilience Plan of the EU affects the environment and the food industry.
- The 2021 – 2022 COVID-19-related social and economic crisis increased food poverty and introduced new challenges forcing the SSE to innovate its responses as mentioned previously.
- The 2022 – Ongoing Russia-Ukraine conflict with its implications on energy prices and food scarcity further increased poverty.
- The City of Milan responded to food emergencies using the experience acquired through the Local Hubs. Using that system as a reference the Food Policy Directorate, the Social Policies Directorate, and the Civil Protection

Directorate organized an extraordinarily good aid mechanism covering the whole city in 4 days.

The legacy of the last decade is also a changed social fabric, especially in the urban suburbs. Food poverty doesn't only affect the extremely poor like in the past but also the working poor and the lower-middle class. New targets have different needs and therefore require different answers.

Inflation, unemployment and poverty have a direct impact on food poverty. Everyone hopes for a **long-term response** to level out inequalities and various **short-term responses** to alleviate contingent problems. An element for change is in the greater awareness of the duality of this issue. More and more people feel that food poverty should be tackled sustainably. Even when we act to alleviate the material needs of deprived people we need to pay greater attention to how and where food is produced, to what diet we are promoting, to what planet's resources we are stimulating and to the level of public health we generate.

4.11 Next challenges

The most significant challenge at the governance level of the entire system is **managing demand in a coordinated way**. The major supporting networks Caritas, Croce Rossa, Banco Alimentare, and QuBì for example collect, process, and analyze data on beneficiary organizations, families, and individuals with little room for data exchange.

Even the actual delivery of service is affected by this fragmentation due both to the confidentiality with which the entities operate and to the privacy legislation which does not allow the sharing of sensitive data. At present, for example, it is not known whether a beneficiary requests and obtains the same type of aid from several different bodies.

Another challenge is the **system's capacity to provide fresh, nutritious food** to beneficiaries with continuity. Food producers and distributors aren't interested in programs other than waste reduction. Recovery of **cooked food from canteens is costly and complex**. There are attempts to involve little organic producers in seasonal markets but still, **organic isn't affordable** at an entry price. Initiatives in the wholesale market and the street markets seem to be the easiest and most feasible to develop in the short term.

4.12 Conflicts

Different approaches among non-profit organizations are part of the SSE system, then there are different visions in public, profit, and non-profit bodies. Such differences are generally non-openly conflictual but some grass-rooted organizations have associative histories more inclined to dialogue and networking than others more inclined to competition. This is seen as normal. Croce Rossa, Caritas, and Banco Alimentare are the three hegemonic organizations and the secondary food aid networks pass through them. As already mentioned for the FWR, the organizations compete in terms of food, human, and financial resources. The theme of cultural hegemony also remains implicit as the biggest organizations hold authoritative positions capable of influencing public policy

and its governance. The City of Milan is positioning itself as a guarantor of good governance and as a place of coordination, discussion, and conciliation of diversity.

4.13 Cultural and Social Context

Milan is a dynamic and prosperous city that recently has attracted a constant flow of workers from many Italian regions, especially from the south. The sharp increase in the cost of living, and the stagnation of salaries have increased poverty and exacerbated relatively new situations such as those of the working poor. The paradoxical situation of growing wealth and contemporary growing poverty also touches food poverty with its diverse ramifications.

As mentioned in the FWR report, any increase or change in social needs is counterbalanced by the spirit of Milan, the very Milanese collective capacity to respond to it. Also, the rich economic fabric of the city helps in many ways. Milan has over 305,400 active companies, the majority of which operate in the tertiary sector, particularly in services, where there are over 158,300 units (51.8% of the total) and 1.27 million employees (58.4%)⁴⁷. A large part of the tertiary sector gravitates around food. Foody for example is the largest wholesale market in Italy and represents an enormous opportunity for the food-related SSE.

4.14 Policy Recommendations

4.14.1 To public administrations:

- Standardizing the simplified bureaucracy applied throughout the COVID-related emergency phase in the usage of funds and resources.
- Facilitating the dual system with food purchased and recovered complementing managing organizations' provisions.
- Expanding visibility and improving the accountability of the system as a whole.
- Enhancing cooperation by activating the whole of the resources available like city departments, publicly owned companies, premises, and social capital.

4.14.2 To FSIs:

- Investing in fundraising leveraging on own networks.
- Create an alternative approach to volunteer recruitment.
- Tighten cooperation with local administration to create conditions for corporate fundraising.
- Using own core values and visions to fuel dialogue with other associations rather than an element of distinction.

4.14.3 To the private sector

- Cooperating with FSIs and public administration to design and implement Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives based on actual community needs.
- Using their core skills to co-design solutions for the communities.

⁴⁷ Assolombarda. Milan Area Key Facts. [Snapshot 2021](#).

4.15 Conclusions

This report considers the main initiatives emerging from the citywide food aid service which expanded the range of products for the organizations in the FEAD system within the city of Milan, the MUFPP policy brief, the Milan Food Policy reports, the interviews with Interviewee 1 (City of Milan), Interviewee 2 (City of Milan), Interviewee 5 (Croce Rossa Italiana), Interviewee 6 (IBVA), Interviewee 2 (Politecnico di Milano) in January and February 2024.

The research centered around the latest urban policies implemented in the domain of social solidarity economy consolidated in the urban practice of food aid for the deprived.

Using Cultivate project research action as a third-party observation point allowed participants from the City of Milan, Non-profit organizations, and the University to provide independent unbiased information and opinions. This helped to draft a more accurate description of barriers and envisage enablers to leverage. Even if Milan could count on the hundreds of independent initiatives on food aid, two main factors (Expo 2015 and the Covid-related social and economic crisis) pushed the City administration to step into a sector originally outside its domain to optimize resources, circulate knowledge and converge interests of many different stakeholders. To make the system sustainable public administrations need to standardize and simplify bureaucracy, facilitate access to a mix of purchased and recovered food, expand visibility, and with the support of academia improve the accountability of the system as a whole. FSIs on the other hand need to create the conditions for a more sustainable and long-term planning with a better fund-raising and people-raising strategy. The private sector has also a key role, weather decide to design and implement Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives based on actual community needs using their core skills to co-design solutions. The City of Milan has provided a safe space for co-competition between NGOs, Companies, Universities, and civil society where potentially everyone wins, the bottom line being vulnerable people with more food available and the environment with less food wasted. Of course, it came at a *taxpayers'* cost, as this setting depends on the political will, and a change in the political scenario may lead to a different outcome.

This all converges on the necessity of an increasingly specific, accurate, and transparent culture of accountability that provides policymakers and citizens with a neat picture.

This seems to be a key point in the short term as food companies, supermarket chains, retailers, NGOs, charities, civil society organizations, public administration departments, and Universities are often reluctant to collect, analyse and share their data.

In the long term, bigger innovations might be needed to confront drastic changes that may occur like a decrease in the available food supply, a lack of volunteers, or a change on the demand side only to name a few. Only a strong alliance among stakeholders would be able to ease the slow and complex bureaucracy, challenge some legal boundaries, and raise the funds necessary to envisage and achieve creative solutions for the food waste and redistribution sector in the years to come.